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A Framework for the Generation of Digital Twins of Cardiac Electrophysiology from Clinical 12-leads ECGs

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Challenge Report

A Framework for the generation of digital twins of cardiac electrophysiology from clinical 12-leads ECGs

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ABSTRACT

Cardiac digital twins (Cardiac Digital Twin (CDT)s) of human electrophysiology (Electrophysiology (EP)) are digital replicas of patient hearts derived from clinical data that match like-for-like all available clinical observations. Due to their inherent predictive potential, CDTs show high promise as a complementary modality aiding in clinical decision making and also in the cost-effective, safe and ethical testing of novel EP device therapies. However, current workflows for both the anatomical and functional twinning phases within CDT generation, referring to the inference of model anatomy and parameters from clinical data, are not sufficiently efficient, robust and accurate for advanced clinical and industrial applications.

Our study addresses three primary limitations impeding the routine generation of high-fidelity CDTs by introducing; a comprehensive parameter vector encapsulating all factors relating to the ventricular EP; an abstract reference frame within the model allowing the unattended manipulation of model parameter fields; a novel fast-forward electrocardiogram (Electrocardiogram (ECG)) model for efficient and biophysically-detailed simulation required for parameter inference. A novel workflow for the generation of CDTs is then introduced as an initial proof of concept.

Anatomical twinning was performed within a reasonable time compatible with clinical workflows (<4h) for 12 subjects from clinically-attained magnetic resonance images. After assessment of the underlying fast forward ECG model against a gold standard bidomain ECG model, functional twinning of optimal parameters according to a clinically-attained 12 lead ECG was then performed using a forward Saltelli sampling approach for a single subject. The achieved results in terms of efficiency and fidelity demonstrate that our workflow is well-suited and viable for generating biophysically-detailed CDTs at scale.

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1. Introduction

Models of cardiac electrophysiology (EP) capable of uniquely replicating like-for-like all available clinical observations for a

given patient are referred to as cardiac digital twins (CDTs) Corral-Acero et al. (2020). Such high fidelity CDTs show high promise as a complementary clinical modality in diagnosis Cartoski et al. (2019), therapy stratification Arevalo et al. (2016) and planning Prakosa et al. (2018) as these may offer predictive potential to be utilized to predetermine the prognosis of acute therapeutic responses within clinical uncertainty. CDTs are also considered a

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powerful new approach for transforming the development and ethical testing of EP device therapies by supporting efficient and robust evaluation of device designs, and can help with the identification of therapeutic mechanisms and optimal device configurations to maximize therapeutic benefits. However, current workflows for generating high fidelity CDTs that are fully personalized in terms of both anatomy and EP to build virtual cohorts at scale are still in a nascent phase [Niederer et al. \(2020\)](#). In general, such CDT workflows comprise two distinct stages, an *anatomical* and a *functional* twinning stage that give rise to various challenges that must be addressed.

At the anatomical twinning stage, tomographic image data are turned into discrete multi-label anatomical meshes [Crozier et al. \(2016\)](#). Depending on the anatomical entities to be included, significant computational resources and numerous manual operator interventions by trained experts may be required to achieve an accurate representation of all anatomical structures of interest and sufficient mesh quality for cardiac EP simulation. Such limitations can only be overcome through a high degree of automation and streamlining of traditionally modular model generation workflows.

Even more demanding is the functional twinning stage, a kind of inverse problem of electrocardiography [Gulrajani et al. \(1989\)](#), where the spatio-temporal behavior of the electrical sources of the heart must be inferred from sparse and noisy clinical ECG data that are afflicted with significant uncertainties. More specifically, electrocardiograms (ECGs) recorded non-invasively from the body surface [Cluitmans et al. \(2018\)](#) can be used to infer electrical information within the heart directly relating to patient-specific cardiac EP parameters within CDTs. In order to facilitate the replication of all clinical observations within a broad highly-variable human population, however, model parameters governing the EP model must be able to account all EP parameters relevant to the genesis of ECGs during sinus-rhythm and be capable of unattended manipulation for optimization procedures. Since many of the numerous parameters vary spatially, an abstract model reference frame encoding intuitive descriptions of location, relative length, or orientation within CDTs is thus warranted. Such an abstract reference frame has been alluded to in previous studies [Bayer et al. \(2018\)](#). Parameters relating to the location, size, and penetration depth of the His-Purkinje system (His-purkinje System (HPS)) or spatially heterogeneous repolarization properties can therefore be mapped to anatomical entities that can be automatically controlled without direct user interaction. Functional twinning workflows for cardiac EP models reported so far in the literature [Potse et al. \(2014\)](#); [Zettinig et al. \(2014\)](#); [Cardone-Noot et al. \(2016\)](#); [Dhamala et al. \(2020\)](#) are primarily limited in this regard.

Solving this inverse problem for functional twinning is then further complicated by the non-uniqueness of the relation between myocardial sources and their signature outside the heart as reflected in an extracellular potential field, and also by the computational costs that incur as a large number of evaluations of the forward model are required. More recently, alternative data-driven methods have started gaining traction [Sermesant et al. \(2006\)](#). These use efficient forward EP models [Pezzuto et al. \(2017\)](#) to generate data for building a regression model to approximate the inverse function of the forward model [Zettinig et al. \(2014\)](#) thus offering an efficient method of estimating model parameters within CDTs. Towards this end, a computationally efficient forward ECG model relating model parameters to simulation outcomes – in terms of a sufficiently-sensitive loss functional – is needed to generate a sufficient amount of data for functional twinning of CDTs with tractable compute resources and within time scales compatible for clinical use ($\ll 1$ day) in various patient interventions.

In this study, we therefore address these limitations in functional twinning and present the following methodological contributions that are crucial for the generation of biophysically-detailed CDTs:

- i. A generic and comprehensive parameter vector that encapsulates all currently known factors governing ventricular activation and repolarization sequences based on functional and histo-anatomical observations [Durrer et al. \(1970\)](#); [Atkinson et al. \(2011\)](#); [Massing and James \(1976\)](#) of the HPS. As such, the parameter vector can be considered complete enough to accommodate, in principle, the variability of macroscopic ventricular EP among human hearts during healthy sinus rhythm [Durrer et al. \(1970\)](#); [Massing and James \(1976\)](#); [Spach et al. \(1963\)](#).
- ii. An abstract reference frame allowing unattended manipulation of both spatially-varying and global parameters within CDTs.
- iii. An efficient and clinically-compatible novel ECG forward model that computes high fidelity gold standard ECGs with close to real-time performance.

A highly automated workflow for building high fidelity EP CDTs that addresses challenges of both anatomical and functional twinning procedures is then introduced as an initial proof of feasibility on a subject within the healthy human population. Building on previous work [Prassl et al. \(2009\)](#); [Crozier et al. \(2016\)](#); [Payer et al. \(2017\)](#), the anatomical twinning procedures have been streamlined and, to a large extent, automated to first generate an anatomically-specific CDT from torso and isotropic 3D whole heart (3D Whole Heart (3DWH)) from cardiac magnetic resonance images (Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)s) for 12 subjects. We then demonstrate the feasibility of our framework to improve model parameters required during functional twinning for only a single subject according to a clinically-attained 12-lead ECG during healthy sinus-rhythm. Saltelli sampling with an L_2 norm loss functional was utilized for this purpose.

2. Methods

Our highly automated workflow first depends on the formulation of an abstract reference frame \mathcal{X} . All spatially-varying model parameters governing ventricular EP, namely the spatial entities of the HPS and repolarization gradients, can be formulated and manipulated without user interaction using this reference frame. A physiologically-detailed comprehensive parameter vector ω is then introduced based on \mathcal{X} to account for the known significant anatomical, structural and physiological variability among human hearts during sinus rhythm [Durrer et al. \(1970\)](#); [Massing and James \(1976\)](#); [Spach et al. \(1963\)](#). We then formulate an efficient forward ECG model and demonstrate its validity by rigorously comparing against the gold-standard model for ECG modeling, the reaction-diffusion (Reaction-Diffusion (R-D)) bidomain model. Finally, an automated workflow for the generation of CDTs is shown to demonstrate feasibility.

2.1. Establishment of an anatomical reference frame

The reference frame \mathcal{X} is based on the introduction of relevant tissue label fields \mathcal{I} , universal torso coordinates (Universal Torso Coordinates (UTC)), and universal ventricular coordinates (Universal Ventricular Coordinates (UVC)) within the model. The computation of UVC within the reference frame \mathcal{X} builds on the fundamental concepts reported in [Bayer et al. \(2018\)](#) (Section 2.1.1), but addresses limitations with regard to robustness and geometric linearity using a bi-Eikonal normalization (Bi-Eikonal Normalization (BN)) method (Section 2.1.2) to replace Laplacian solutions.

The same BN method was also used for computation of the UTC. Bijective functions (\mathcal{B}) were then defined to dictate conversions between the abstract anatomical domains within \mathcal{X} and Cartesian spaces to allow automated control of all spatially-varying parameters as discussed in Section 2.2. For more information about tissue label fields \mathcal{I} and the computation of UTC, please refer to supplemental Secs. 1 and 2.

2.1.1. Universal ventricular coordinates

Our previous report of Laplacian-based UVCs Bayer et al. (2018) introduced novel coordinates for describing positions within the ventricles in anatomical terms based on the notion of a long axis, z (from apex towards the ventricular basis), transmural, ρ (from endocardium to epicardium), circumferential, φ (septal, infero-septal, inferior, lateral, anterior, antero-septal) and chamber association, ν (left versus right). To improve geometric robustness and automate the computation of UVCs the following extensions were implemented:

- i Automatic extraction of mesh surfaces and interfaces using boolean set operations according to the tissue labels \mathcal{I} .
- ii Alternative definitions of Dirichlet BCs, namely through the introduction of separate apices in the left ventricle (Left Ventricle (LV)) and the right ventricle (Right Ventricle (RV)).
- iii Enhanced computation of UVC fields using the novel BN method (see Section 2.1.2).

A visualization of the updated UVCs can be seen in the supplementary material, Section 3.

2.1.2. Bi-Eikonal normalization method

Implementation of the BN method is based on the isotropic Eikonal equation given by the non-linear partial differential equation

$$\begin{cases} \|\nabla t(\mathbf{x})\| = \sqrt{\nabla t(\mathbf{x})^\top \nabla t(\mathbf{x})} = 1 & \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \\ t(\mathbf{x}) = 0 & \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{S} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $t(\mathbf{x}) \geq 0$ is the arrival time of a traveling wave with source $\mathcal{S} \subset \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ at a point $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$. Since there is no preferred direction, the arrival time can be written as $t(\mathbf{x}) = l(\mathbf{x})v^{-1}$ where v is the constant propagation velocity of the wave and $l(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the length of the shortest path between \mathcal{S} and \mathbf{x} . For two sources $\mathcal{S}_1 \subset \Omega$ and $\mathcal{S}_2 \subset \Omega$, Eq. (1) yields two solutions t_1 and t_2 , respectively. By setting

$$\xi(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t_1(\mathbf{x}) + t_2(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \\ \frac{t_1(\mathbf{x})}{t_1(\mathbf{x}) + t_2(\mathbf{x})} = \frac{l_1(\mathbf{x})}{l_1(\mathbf{x}) + l_2(\mathbf{x})}, & \text{else,} \end{cases}$$

the function $\xi : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies $\xi(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{S}_1$ and $\xi(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{S}_2 \setminus \mathcal{S}_1$ by construction.

While the BN method is computationally more costly than its Laplacian counterpart, it is geometrically more robust and achieves better linearity. A comparison of the Laplacian and BN method solutions can be found in the supplemental Section 4.

2.2. Control of spatial parameters using bijective mapping

Bijective mappings were numerically implemented using an efficient custom-built kd-tree algorithm. The bijective mapping for LV and RV within UVC for \mathcal{B} is defined as

$$\mathcal{B}_{\text{UVC}_V} : \Omega_{\text{LV}} \rightarrow D_{\text{UVC}_V} \quad \text{with} \\ D_{\text{UVC}_V} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi) \mid z \in [0, 1], \rho \in [0, 1], \varphi \in (-\pi, +\pi)\}$$

and

$$\mathcal{B}_{\text{UVC}_R} : \Omega_{\text{RV}} \rightarrow D_{\text{UVC}_R} \quad \text{with} \\ D_{\text{UVC}_R} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi) \mid z \in [0, 1], \rho \in [0, 1], \varphi \in (-\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{+\pi}{2})\},$$

respectively. Both mappings are summarized to one bijective function

$$\mathcal{B}_{\text{UVC}} : \Omega_{\text{biv}} \rightarrow D_{\text{UVC}} \quad \text{with} \\ D_{\text{UVC}} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi, \nu) \mid \nu \in \{-1, +1\}, (z, \rho, \varphi) \in D_{\text{UVC}_V} \text{ or } D_{\text{UVC}_R}\}$$

which facilitates the unique parametrization of Ω_{biv} , i.e. for all \mathbf{x} in Ω_{biv} there exists a unique $\mathbf{b} = (z, \rho, \varphi, \nu) \in D_{\text{UVC}}$ such that $\mathbf{x} = \mathcal{B}_{\text{UVC}}^{-1}(\mathbf{b})$ holds. The bijective mapping for UTC within \mathcal{B} is defined as

$$\mathcal{B}_{\text{UTC}} : \Omega_{\text{tor}} \rightarrow D_{\text{UTC}} \quad \text{with} \\ D_{\text{UTC}} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi) \mid z \in [0, 1], \rho \in [0, 1], \varphi \in (-\pi, +\pi)\}$$

which allows a unique parameterization of the torso model Ω_{tor} , i.e. for all $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{\text{tor}}$ there exists a unique $\mathbf{e} = (z, \rho, \varphi) \in D_{\text{UTC}}$ such that $\mathbf{x} = \mathcal{B}_{\text{UTC}}^{-1}(\mathbf{e})$ holds.

2.3. Definition of a parameter vector describing ventricular electrophysiology during sinus rhythm

The genesis of the ventricular ECG is governed by the spatio-temporal distribution of cardiac sources throughout the ventricles that set up an extracellular potential field in the torso. The source distribution for a given ventricular anatomy over a cycle covering activation and repolarization and the ECG wave forms linked to these are dictated by four factors: i) the HPS swiftly distributing depolarization wave fronts to the ventricular subendocardium (Subendocardial (SE)) to initiate propagation in the ventricular myocardium; ii) the orthotropic and spatially heterogeneous conduction velocity (Conduction Velocity (CV)) of depolarization wave fronts within the ventricles; iii) intrinsic spatially varying action potential duration (Action Potential Duration (APD)) and shape governing repolarization; and, iv) the conductivity of the surrounding torso governing ECG signal magnitudes, and its heterogeneity influencing current distribution and thus modulating ECG wave forms by distortion of the extracellular potential field. We encapsulate these factors into a high-dimensional parameter vector ω governing a large portion of macroscopic ventricular EP. A complete list of all parameters is available in supplemental Section 6.

2.3.1. His-Purkinje system

Depolarization of the ventricles is initiated by the HPS. While direct measurement of the topology of the HPS is not feasible, experimental mapping studies suggest the notion of a fascicular conduction system comprising N number of fascicles. Due to the high CV within the HPS and the dense network of Purkinje fibers around the earliest site of ventricular activation of a given fascicle, referred to as root point, it is assumed that the tissue patches adjacent to the fascicles activate almost instantaneously. For the sake of geometric simplicity, we define the junctional regions of the fascicles to be of disk-like shape. Thus, a fascicular-based HPS stimulus profile can be formulated where each fascicle is abstractly defined within \mathcal{X} by $\mathbf{x}_i = (\mathbf{b}, \delta_\rho, \delta_{\varphi z}, t)$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, where $\mathbf{b} \in D_{\text{UVC}}$ is the root point located at the center of the disk, $\delta_\rho > 0$ is the spatial extent along the transmural axis, $\delta_{\varphi z} > 0$ is the radius of the disk in the apico-basal-circumferential plane (Fig. 1) and $t \geq 0$ indicates the activation time.

Furthermore, beyond the immediate junctional patches of the HPS around root points we assume a diffuse network of Purkinje fibers of unknown topology to reside predominantly within a SE layer that is characterized by conductive electrical properties differing from the general myocardium Li et al. (1998); Kassebaum and Van Dyke (1966); Keith and Flack (2004); Massing and James (1976); Spach et al. (1963); Opthof et al. (2017); Glukhov et al. (2010); Keller et al. (2012). In particular, the spread of activation within the SE layer

Fig. 1. Definition of terminal fascicles of the HPS in UVC space and mapping onto biventricular model.

away from the terminal ends of the fascicle appears to occur at higher CVs than in the bulk myocardial wall due to the combined effect of the fast-conducting properties of the HPS [Draper and Weidmann \(1951\)](#) and, potentially, by a more abundant expression of sodium channels in SE myocytes [Remme et al. \(2009\)](#). These SE layers in LV $\Omega_{SE,lv}$ and RV $\Omega_{SE,rv}$ are defined as

$$\Omega_{SE,lv} = \mathcal{B}_{UVC,lv}^{-1}(D_{SE,lv}) \quad \text{and} \quad \Omega_{SE,rv} = \mathcal{B}_{UVC,rv}^{-1}(D_{SE,rv})$$

with

$$D_{SE,lv} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi) \in D_{UVC,lv} \mid z \in [z_{min,lv}, z_{max,lv}], \rho \in [\rho_{min,lv}, \rho_{max,lv}]\}$$

$$D_{SE,rv} = \{(z, \rho, \varphi) \in D_{UVC,rv} \mid z \in [z_{min,rv}, z_{max,rv}], \rho \in [\rho_{min,rv}, \rho_{max,rv}]\}$$

for $z_{min,\nu} < z_{max,\nu}$, $\rho_{min,\nu} < \rho_{max,\nu}$ and $\nu \in \{lv, rv\}$.

2.3.2. Ventricular conduction

CV of depolarization wavefronts within the ventricular wall is characterized by a spatially varying orthotropic tensor field [Durrer et al. \(1970\)](#). CV at each point in space differs along the orthotropic eigenaxes of the tissue – along the prevailing myocyte orientation aka fibers, $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, within sheets, $\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x})$, and in a sheet-normal direction, $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$. Using the CVs along $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ as reference, off-axis CVs in each region were defined by respective ratios, i.e $c_{\mathbf{d},reg,\nu} = r_{\mathbf{d},reg,\nu} c_{reg,\nu}$ with $\mathbf{d} \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{n}\}$, $reg \in \{myo, se\}$ and $\nu \in \{lv, rv\}$.

While the eigenaxes of the ventricular myocardium can be attained, in principle, through diffusion-tensor imaging [Helm et al. \(2005\)](#); [Stephenson et al. \(2017\)](#), their acquisition has not become clinical routine yet. Moreover, acquired data are noisy and of low resolution, limiting their utility for modeling purposes. Therefore, we use a rule-based representation of fiber and sheet arrangement [Bayer et al. \(2012\)](#). Applied rules are rooted in physiology [Streeter et al. \(1969\)](#); [Fernandez-Teran and Hurle \(1982\)](#) assuming a linear rotation of the fiber angle transmurally from the endocardium to epicardium within both ventricles,

$$\alpha_{septum}(d) = (1-d)\alpha_{endo} - d\alpha_{epi},$$

$$\alpha_{wall}(d) = (1-d)\alpha_{endo} + d\alpha_{epi}$$

$$\beta_{septum}(d) = (1-d)\beta_{endo} - d\beta_{epi},$$

$$\beta_{wall}(d) = (1-d)\beta_{endo} + d\beta_{epi}$$

where α and β correspond to the longitudinal and transverse fiber angles, respectively, and d is the normalized transmural depth.

2.3.3. Ventricular repolarization

The combined effect of activation sequence and intrinsic APD heterogeneity of the human heart defines ventricular dispersion of repolarization which is the electrical source governing the genesis of the T-wave [Keller et al. \(2012\)](#); [Ophthof et al. \(2016, 2017\)](#); [Glukhov et al. \(2010\)](#); [Li et al. \(1998\)](#). Ventricular, transmural, apico-basal, and anterior-posterior repolarization gradients were taken into account by defining a map APD(\mathbf{x}) based on gradient fields [Burgess et al. \(1966\)](#) inherently present in D_{UVC} . Note that only heterogeneities in APD were taken into account. More subtle effects due to heterogeneity in action potential shapes were ignored as the Mitchell Schaeffer (MS) model is not able to replicate variable morphologies. First, a linear combination, q , was defined and weighted according to $\mathbf{q}_w = (z_d, \rho_d, \varphi_d, v_d) \in \mathbb{R}^4$ along each UVC coordinate, allowing to control the relative influence of individual gradients. The result is then mapped into a physiological range of APDs specified by APD_{min} and APD_{max}. In this case APD is taken as the duration of the action potential at 90% repolarization. Accordingly, APD(\mathbf{x}) is defined:

$$q(\mathbf{x}) = \rho(\mathbf{x}) \rho_d + v(\mathbf{x}) v_d + z(\mathbf{x}) z_d + \sigma(\varphi(\mathbf{x})) \varphi_d \quad (2)$$

$$APD(\mathbf{x}) = \left(\left(\frac{q(\mathbf{x}) - \min(q(\mathbf{x}))}{\max(q(\mathbf{x})) - \min(q(\mathbf{x}))} \right) (APD_{max} - APD_{min}) + APD_{min} \right) \quad (3)$$

with sign function σ and $(z(\mathbf{x}), \rho(\mathbf{x}), \varphi(\mathbf{x}), v(\mathbf{x})) = \mathcal{B}_{UVC}(\mathbf{x})$. Note the weights allow for gradient direction reversal required to match experimental observations. A relationship between values of relevant parameters ω_{ion} of the selected ionic model and APD must be formulated as later discussed in [Section 2.4](#) and seen in other modeling studies [Relan et al. \(2011\)](#).

2.3.4. Conductivities

Intracellular and extracellular conductivities, g_{i*} and g_{e*} , with $* = \{f, s, n\}$ denoting the eigenaxes, were assigned globally within the ventricles, without any spatial variations. Myocardial intra- and extracellular conductivity tensors were given then by

$$\mathbf{g}_{\xi}(\mathbf{x}) = g_{\xi f}(\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})) + g_{\xi s}(\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x})) + g_{\xi n}(\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})) \quad (4)$$

with $\xi = \{i, e\}$ denoting the intra- and extracellular space. Conductivity within the lungs, atrial myocardium, and blood pools were assigned separate isotropic values that varied from the

remaining tissues in the torso and heart Keller et al. (2010); Roberts and Scher (1982); Sebastian et al. (2008); Clerc (1976); Roberts et al. (1979); Le Guyader et al. (2001). The complete conductivity vector for the model was then defined:

$$\mathbf{g} = (\mathbf{g}_{ef}, \mathbf{g}_{es}, \mathbf{g}_{en}, \mathbf{g}_{if}, \mathbf{g}_{is}, \mathbf{g}_{in}, \mathbf{g}_{lungs}, \mathbf{g}_{blood}, \mathbf{g}_{atria}, \mathbf{g}_{torso}).$$

2.3.5. Electrode placements

Any number $M \in \mathbb{N}$ of electrode locations within Ω_{tor} to compute electrograms on the body surface can be defined by introducing $\mathbf{e}_j \in D_{\text{UTC}}$ based on UTCs for $j \in \{1, \dots, M\}$. In this study $M = 10$ electrode locations were defined to reconstruct the 12-lead ECG system according to Halhuber et al. (2012). For the sake of convenience, the ECG vector elements are labeled corresponding to their respective lead, i.e. $y_{m,l}(t)$ and $y_{s,l}(t)$ denote the measured and simulated ECG signal, respectively, for lead $l \in E$ with

$$E = \{\text{I, II, III, aVR, aVL, aVF, V1, V2, V3, V4, V5, V6}\}.$$

2.4. Fast-forward ECG model

EP activity within the ventricles was modeled using an efficient and clinically-compatible finite-element (Finite Element Method (FEM)) model for simulations of ECGs from ω . The fast-forward ECG achieves close to real-time performance by building on the reaction-Eikonal (Reaction-Eikonal (R-E)) model Neic et al. (2017) combined with the computationally efficient Mitchell Schaeffer (MS) ionic model Mitchell and Schaeffer (2003) representing cellular dynamics, to simulate action potential, $V_m(\mathbf{x}, t)$, propagation and to compute ventricular source distributions driving the extracellular potential field $\phi_e(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and a lead-field based approach Geselowitz (1989); Potse (2018) to recover electrograms for ECG computation. We term the R-E approach paired with the lead field projection the Reaction-Eikonal Lead Field (RELf) formulation for simplicity.

The R-E model, previously described in great detail elsewhere Neic et al. (2017), couples an Eikonal-based activation with the physiological monodomain source model. Briefly, compared to a standard R-D model as detailed in 2.4.1, the R-E approach offers two distinct advantages during activation: First, the propagation of wavefronts can be computed on coarser meshes without introducing marked discretization artifacts as it is the case when using R-D models Niederer et al. (2011b). Secondly, CVs are direct input parameters, thus avoiding their indirect determination by estimating appropriate tissue conductivities to obtain the sought after velocities Costa et al. (2013).

In the R-E forward model wavefront propagation is described by the anisotropic Eikonal model given as

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt{\nabla t_a^T \mathbf{V} \nabla t_a} = 1 & \text{in } \Omega_{\text{biv}} \\ t_a = t_0 & \text{in } \Gamma \end{cases}$$

where t_a is a positive function describing the wavefront arrival time at any location $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_{\text{biv}}$, t_0 are the instants of initial activations at locations Γ corresponding to the terminal ends of the fascicular bundles, and the tensor field \mathbf{V} encodes the spatially heterogeneous orthotropic squared CV by:

$$\mathbf{V}(\mathbf{x}) := c_f^2(\mathbf{x}) (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})) + c_s^2(\mathbf{x}) (\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x})) + c_n^2(\mathbf{x}) (\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}) \otimes \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})) \quad (5)$$

The solution t_a is used then to solve the parabolic part of a standard R-D model in mono- or bidomain mode with an additional stimulus current, $I_{\text{foot}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, depending on the arrival time t_a . This model referred to as $R - E^+$ is given as

$$C_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} = I_{\text{foot}} + \frac{1}{\beta} \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\xi \{ \phi_i | V_m \} - I_{\text{ion}} \quad (6)$$

where $\xi = \{i|m\}$ denotes intracellular or harmonic mean monodomain tensor Bishop and Plank (2011b), respectively, with

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_m = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_e)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_e,$$

$V_m(\mathbf{x})$ the transmembrane voltage, ϕ_i the intracellular potential, β the bidomain surface-to-volume ratio and I_{ion} the ionic current. The current driving the foot of the action potential is given by

$$I_{\text{foot}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \begin{cases} I_{\text{foot}}(t) & \text{if } t \in [t_a(\mathbf{x}) - T_{\text{foot}}, t_a(\mathbf{x})] \text{ and } V_m(\mathbf{x}, t) < V_{\text{th}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where T_{foot} is the duration of the foot of an action potential, V_{th} is the excitation threshold of a given ionic model and the temporal definition of I_{foot} is defined as

$$I_{\text{foot}}(t) = -C_m \frac{dV_{\text{foot}}}{dt} \quad (8)$$

with V_{foot} describing the shape of the foot of the action potential. V_{foot} is either prescribed from a foot of a simulated propagating depolarization wave front or a fitted exponential function is used Neic et al. (2017). Analog to R-D models, the R-E model can be set up in monodomain mode, yielding the transmembrane voltage $V_m(\mathbf{x})$, or in pseudo-bidomain mode yielding, in addition, extracellular potentials $\phi_e(\mathbf{x})$ Bishop and Plank (2011a).

A further simplification is the omission of the diffusion term in Eq. (6) yielding the R-E⁻ model given by

$$C_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} = I_{\text{foot}} - I_{\text{ion}}. \quad (9)$$

Thus solving the R-E⁻ model is substantially cheaper than the R-E⁺ model as only local problems have to be solved. Unlike with R-D models this is feasible as propagation is mediated by the stimulus term I_{foot} and not by diffusion. In the R-E model the diffusion term plays a very minor role in wave front propagation, but acts during repolarization to smooth out intrinsic APD gradients.

The phenomenological MS model was chosen to represent cellular dynamics due to its computational efficiency and its ability to provide a direct relationship between parameters within the model and APD necessary for implementing repolarization heterogeneity. The entire MS model can be formulated by:

$$\begin{aligned} v_m &= \frac{V_m - V_{\text{min}}}{V_{\text{max}} - V_{\text{min}}} \\ J_{\text{in}} &= \frac{h v_m^2 (1 - v_m)}{\tau_{\text{in}}} \\ J_{\text{out}} &= -\frac{v_m}{\tau_{\text{out}}} \\ I_{\text{ion}} &= -(V_{\text{max}} - V_{\text{min}}) (J_{\text{in}} + J_{\text{out}}) \\ \frac{dh}{dt} &= \begin{cases} \frac{1-h}{\tau_{\text{open}}}, & \text{if } v_m < v_{m,\text{gate}} \\ \frac{-h}{\tau_{\text{close}}}, & \text{if } v_m > v_{m,\text{gate}} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where the time constants $\tau_{\text{in}} \ll \tau_{\text{out}} \ll \tau_{\text{open}}, \tau_{\text{close}}$ determine the morphology of the action potential and v_m is the normalized transmembrane voltage. Thus, the parameter vector for the MS ionic model, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\text{ion,MS}}$, can be formulated by:

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{\text{ion,MS}} = (\tau_{\text{close}}, \tau_{\text{in}}, \tau_{\text{out}}, \tau_{\text{open}}, V_{\text{min}}, V_{\text{max}})$$

Since extracellular potentials ϕ_e and, thus, the ECG depend on the term $\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i \nabla V_m) v_m$ must be scaled back to physiological values in the assumed voltage range between V_{min} and V_{max} corresponding to the resting and peak transmembrane voltage, respectively. A relationship can then be formulated between APD and the parameter τ_{close} dictating APD, such that:

$$\tau_{\text{close}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\text{APD}(\mathbf{x})}{\ln\left(\frac{v_{\text{in}}}{v_{\text{out}}}\right)}.$$

Fig. 2. Generalized workflow for the generation of CDTs. Anatomical twinning involves multi-label segmentation of MRIs to generate anatomical meshes representing the heart and torso. A reference frame \mathcal{X} is established within the anatomical meshes to allow for unattended manipulation of model parameters defined by a parameter vector, ω , governing ventricular EP. A fast-forward ECG model computes simulated ECGs y_s that are compared to the measured clinical ECGs, y_m , by a loss functional \mathcal{L} . Model parameters can be updated through parameter optimization to achieve better simulation outcomes.

Projection of electrical potentials onto the ECG electrode locations at the body surface were modelled by the lead field formulation as proposed in Potse (2018). The lead field is computed as the potential field resulting from a unit current injected at \mathbf{e} and withdrawn at \mathbf{r} by

$$\nabla \cdot ((\sigma_i + \sigma_e) \nabla Z(\mathbf{x})) = I_e \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{e}) - I_r \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{r}) \quad (10)$$

where $\|I_e\| = \|I_r\| = 1$ are unitary currents and δ is Dirac's delta function. The lead field method yields ϕ_e at chosen discrete locations, \mathbf{e} , corresponding to electrode placements relative to the location of the reference electrode at \mathbf{r} . ECGs are computed at the body surface then by

$$\phi_e(\mathbf{e}) = \int_{\Omega_{\text{div}}} \nabla Z \cdot \sigma_i \nabla V_m \, d\mathbf{x} \quad (11)$$

where σ_i is the intracellular conductivity tensor and ϕ_e reflects the extracellular electrogram recorded at locations in E relative to the reference location \mathbf{r} . Using the FEM the lead field integral is readily evaluated by a vector-matrix product between intracellular stiffness matrix and the pointwise vector product between V_m and Z . The lower right abdominal electrode within E served as reference location \mathbf{r} .

2.4.1. Assessment according to gold standard bidomain ECG

The full R-D bidomain model provides the most physiologically-realistic representation of cardiac bioelectric activity at the organ scale yielding V_m and ϕ_e at every point in space and time, implicitly accounting for the effects of bath-loading upon wavefront dynamics through representation of a surrounding conductive media such as blood pool or torso. The R-D bidomain equations can be recast and solved in the elliptic-parabolic form given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\nabla \cdot (\sigma_i + \sigma_e) \nabla \phi_e \\ -\nabla \cdot \sigma_b \nabla \phi_e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \nabla \cdot \sigma_i \nabla V_m \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$\beta C_m \frac{\partial V_m}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \sigma_i \nabla (V_m + \phi_e) - \beta (I_{\text{ion}}(V_m, \boldsymbol{\eta}) - I_s(\mathbf{x}_f, t_0))$, (13) where I_s is a stimulus current applied at the defined fascicular locations \mathbf{x}_f at instant t_0 . If the solution of V_m used on the right hand side of is based on eq. (13), the model is referred to as full bidomain.

Assumptions and simplifications underlying the fast-forward RELF⁻ and RELF⁺ models as detailed in Secs. 2.3 and 2.4 on computed ECG morphology was investigated in reference to this gold standard. Specifically, four potential sources of errors were considered:

- i. Activation spread is driven by the term I_{foot} in (7) that depends on the Eikonal solution t_a . Thus downstream loading effects upon propagation velocity and wavefront profiles are neglected
- ii. The use of coarser meshes to speed up computations may impact the fidelity of the cardiac source representation
- iii. ECGs computed using the lead-field formulation may deviate from gold standard bidomain ECG
- iv. Omitting the diffusion term in the RELF⁻ model preserves intrinsic repolarization which may entail an overestimation of the T-wave in the ECG.

For thorough assessment, the extracellular potential fields ϕ_e were recovered from source distributions $V_m(\mathbf{x})$ that were computed by solving R-E⁺ or R-E⁻ models according to Eq. (6) in monodomain configuration or Eq. (9). In both cases, the extracellular potential field ϕ_e does not exert any loading effects on the tissue. As such, the model is referred to as pseudo-bidomain. For further details we refer to Bishop and Plank (2011b,a). The experimental setup for this validation is described later within Section 2.6.

2.5. Workflow for cardiac digital twinning

An overall workflow with all major processing stages for the automated generation of CDTs is conceptually illustrated in Fig. 2. The entire workflow was implemented in the open source python-based <https://git.opencarp.org/openCARP/carputils> carputils framework which integrated the CARPentry simulator Vigmond et al. (2008); Augustin et al. (2016); Neic et al. (2017) and the open source finite element mesh and data manipulation software <https://bitbucket.org/aneic/meshtool/src/master/> meshtool Neic et al. (2020); Neic (0000).

2.5.1. Acquisition of clinical images and measured ECGs

A data set consisting of 12 healthy adult volunteers (8 male, 4 female), hereafter referred to as S_1 , was attained according to a standardized protocol that included torso and isotropic 3DWH cardiac MRI at 3T (Magnetom Skyra, Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany). The full torso MRI was acquired in four overlapping transversal stacks of a non-ECG gated 3D T1-weighted gradient-echo sequence in expiration. The spatial resolution was non-isotropic ($1.3 \times 1.3 \times 3.0 \text{ mm}^3$). A higher-resolved ($0.7 \times 0.7 \times 0.7 \text{ mm}^3$), ECG-gated, fat-saturated, T2-prepared, isotropic 3D gradient-echo sequence employing navigators was used to image

the heart and the surrounding vessels in the expiratory state during free breathing (3DWH). In-plane spatial deformations caused by gradient in-homogeneity as well as signal-intensity variations from the array coils were automatically corrected during image reconstruction. This MRI study was approved by the ethical review board of the Medical University of Graz (EKNr: 24–126 ex 11/12) and all subjects gave written informed consent.

Before MRI acquisition, a 12 lead ECG acquired in a supine position using MRI-compatible electrodes was recorded with a custom in-house ECG device to ensure access to digital data and control of filter settings. Deviating from the clinical standard, limb leads were placed at the torso – right and left arm and leg electrodes at left and right upper chest and lower abdomen, respectively – and the electrodes were left *in situ* during imaging to facilitate the exact recovery of electrode positions later in the model. The acquired signals were filtered using low pass and high pass second-order Bessel filters according to clinical standards at 60Hz and 0.05Hz Luo and Johnston (2010). A 50Hz band-stop Bessel filter had also been applied for removal of electrical noise.

2.5.2. Generation of anatomically-specific models

A FEM computational mesh with specific tissue label fields \mathcal{I} was constructed from detailed segmentations. Automated 3DWH segmentation was implemented using an adaption of a convolutional neural network within Tensorflow according to Payer et al. (2017); Zhuang et al. (2019) with manual corrections performed using the open source software Seg3D CIBC (2016). Torso MRIs were segmented using threshold-based filters in conjunction with boolean operations in Seg3D. To correct for breathing displacement between 3DWH and torso MRI scans, the 3DWH segmentation was registered into the torso using an improvised iterative closest point algorithm in Seg3D Besl and McKay (1992).

Unstructured, conformal, boundary-fitted anatomical torso meshes were then generated directly from the registered multi-label segmentations. An image-based mesh generation technique was used that applies the dual mesh of an octree directly to segmented 3D image stacks Prassl et al. (2009), as implemented in the mesh generation software Tarantula (CAE Software Solutions, Eggenburg, Austria). In all cases, a target average mesh resolution of the heart of $1000\mu m$ was chosen, which was deemed adequate for EP simulations using a R-E model Neic et al. (2017). For subject S_1 , additional meshes were generated at finer target resolutions of $500\mu m$ and $250\mu m$ to test computational scaling of the pipeline within a spatial resolution range required for simulations of ventricular EP using standard R-D models Crozier et al. (2016). The interface between heart and torso meshes were kept conforming, but adaptive coarsening of the torso mesh with distance from the epicardial surface was allowed.

The extraction of the various surfaces and interfaces required for the generation of the UTCs and UVCs were automated using *meshtool* for performing boolean set operations according to the tissue labels \mathcal{I} , for extraction and reinsertion of the bi-ventricular sub-domain Ω_{biv} , as well as for mapping of all associated surfaces between the two domains Ω_{biv} and Ω_{tor} . Additional regions, such as apical nodes and circumferential planar interfaces, were extracted by means of plane intersections in auxiliary functions. Atrial structures were also segmented and meshed, but as these were not electrically active in the EP model no atrial reference frame was generated Roney et al. (2019).

2.5.3. Alignment of simulated ECGs to clinical ECGs

Measured, $\mathbf{y}_m : [0, T_m] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{12}$, and simulated, $\mathbf{y}_s : [0, T_s] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{12}$ with $T_s < T_m$, 12 lead ECGs, are shifted in time and, inevitably, differ in absolute magnitude and signal offsets. For each lead $l \in E$ the

Table 1

Constant parameter values assigned within ω_0 based on experimental assumptions and clinically-derived measurements. The ν within the SE layer and CV parameters pertains to the ventricular coordinate, indicating the same value was prescribed to both the LV and the RV.

Entity	Parameter	Value	Unit
SE Layer	$\rho_{\min, \nu}$	0.0	-
	$\rho_{\max, \nu}$	0.3	-
	$z_{\min, \nu}$	0.15	-
	$z_{\max, \nu}$	0.9	-
Myocardial Fibers	α_{epi}	-60	°
	α_{endo}	60	°
	β_{endo}	-65	°
Conduction Velocity	β_{epi}	25	°
	$c_{\text{myo}, \nu}$	0.57	m/s
	$c_{\text{se}, \nu}$	2.0	m/s
Conductivities	$r_{d, \text{reg}, \nu}$	0.42	-
	g_{if}	0.34	S/m
	g_{ef}	0.17	S/m
	g_{is}	0.06	S/m
	g_{es}	0.08	S/m
	g_{in}	0.06	S/m
	g_{en}	0.08	S/m
	g_{lungs}	0.0389	S/m
	g_{blood}	0.7	S/m
	g_{torso}	0.22	S/m
g_{atria}	0.0537	S/m	

Table 2

Tuned parameter settings for $\omega_{\text{ion}, \text{MS}}$ of the MS model defined within ω_0 to match the corresponding TNNP ionic model AP.

Parameter	Value	Unit
τ_{in}	0.3	ms
τ_{out}	5.4	ms
τ_{open}	80.	ms
τ_{close}	175.	ms
V_{min}	-86.2	mV
V_{max}	40.0	mV

time-instances $t_{m,l} \in [0, T_m]$ and $t_{s,l} \in [0, T_s]$ were determined as

$$t_{m,l} = \underset{t \in [0, T_m]}{\text{argmax}} |y_{m,l}^2(t)| \quad \text{and} \quad t_{s,l} = \underset{t \in [0, T_s]}{\text{argmax}} |y_{s,l}^2(t)|$$

respectively. The temporal shift $\delta t_l = t_{m,l} - t_{s,l}$ was then used to compute the L_2 -optimal scaling factor $s_l \in \mathbb{R}$ and offset $r_l \in \mathbb{R}$ by minimizing the L_2 norm

$$\int_0^{T_s} |y_{m,l}(t + \delta t_l) - (s_l y_{s,l}(t) + r_l)|^2 dt \quad (14)$$

providing a transformation tuple $(\delta t_l, s_l, r_l)$. The scaling factor and offset aim to cancel out any factors not related to ECG morphology. Since these factors are the same for all 12 recorded signals, the transformation tuple must be the same for all signals as well. Among all the 12 transformation tuples $(\delta t_l, s_l, r_l)$, one for each $l \in E$, the optimal tuple was selected as $(\delta t_{\text{opt}}, s_{\text{opt}}, r_{\text{opt}}) = (\delta t_{l_{\text{opt}}}, s_{l_{\text{opt}}}, r_{l_{\text{opt}}})$ with

$$l_{\text{opt}} = \underset{l \in E}{\text{argmin}} \left(\sum_{k \in E} \int_0^{T_s} |y_{m,k}(t + \delta t_l) - (s_l y_{s,k}(t) + r_l)|^2 dt \right)$$

yielding the smallest overall loss given by the sum of all individual errors. Note that this optimization procedure selects the best alignment, scale and offset according to one lead, and applies the tuple to all leads for consistency of the signals.

2.5.4. Initialization of the parameter vector

A parameter sub-vector ω_0 was first initialized based on values as reported in the literature and a series of preliminary simulations which solely aimed at obtaining suitable QRS durations, see Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. Constant parameters within ω_0

Table 3

Placement of $M = 10$ electrodes for subject S_1 localized to D_{UTC} as prescribed within ω_0 . Note all parameters are unitless.

Electrode	z	φ
e_{RA}	0.84	-0.67
e_{LA}	0.89	-2.59
e_{LL}	0.06	-2.80
e_{RL}	0.02	-0.48
e_{V1}	0.48	-1.22
e_{V2}	0.46	-2.05
e_{V3}	0.42	-2.29
e_{V4}	0.42	-2.51
e_{V5}	0.43	-2.79
e_{V6}	0.43	3.14

included:

$$\omega_0 = (z_{\min,v}, z_{\max,v}, \rho_{\min,v}, \rho_{\max,v}, c_{\text{reg},v}, r_{\text{d,reg},v}, \alpha_{\text{endo}}, \alpha_{\text{epi}}, \beta_{\text{endo}}, \beta_{\text{epi}}, \omega_{\text{ion}}, \mathbf{g}, M, E). \quad (15)$$

CV within the ventricular myocardium was then prescribed according to Roberts and Scher (1982) such that $c_{\text{myo},v} = 0.57\text{ms}^{-1}$ along the fiber direction and a value of $c_{\text{se},v} = 2.0\text{ms}^{-1}$ was prescribed within the fast-conducting SE layer according to Durrer et al. (1970). Off-axis CVs in sheet and sheet-normal directions were set relative to the fiber velocity using a ratio of $r_{\text{d,reg},v} = 0.42$ for both, i.e. CVs were assumed transversely isotropic, to match conductive anisotropy within the source model in keeping with Roberts and Scher (1982). Myocardial fiber architecture was defined according to Streeter et al. (1969), and geometrical cutoffs for the SE layers were assigned values according to anatomical observations as reported in Massing and James (1976); Spach et al. (1963); Stephenson et al. (2017) and modeling studies Potse et al. (2009). The torso volume-conductor model was then prescribed conductivities according to the average values reported in Keller et al. (2010).

Additional parameters ω_{ion} for the MS model morphology were also included in ω_0 as detailed in Section 2.4. Such MS parameters were manually adjusted according to the more biophysically detailed Ten Tusscher ionic model of human ventricular myocytes (Ten-Tusscher Ionic Model (TNNP)) that serves as a gold standard for ionic modeling Ten Tusscher and Panfilov (2006).

Lastly, exact electrode placements E for S_1 for 12 lead ECG construction were localized within Ω_{TOR} as detailed in Table 3 and incorporated into ω_0 . The average resolution of the torso surface for S_1 was approximately 4.2mm.

2.5.5. Parameter estimation using saltelli sampling

We attempted to identify a subject-specific parameter vector ω_{opt} that replicates the ECG morphology of a single subject S_1 with high fidelity using Saltelli sampling Saltelli et al. (2010); Saltelli (2002). The Saltelli sampling is a quasi-Monte Carlo method extending the Sobol sampling, designed to place sample points as uniformly as possible in the sampling space, see Kucherenko et al. (2015). Due to the dependency of repolarization on activation, two Saltelli parameterization sweeps were carried out consecutively.

In a first sweep, only the activation phase pertaining to the QRS complex was considering by taking a feature sub-vector, ω_{QRS} , confined to a time window of $0 \leq t < 120\text{ms}$ relating to physiologically relative ranges for QRS duration during sinus rhythm. Owing to the high dimensionality of the complete parameter vector, only a subset of key model parameters defined in (16) relating to the HPS were considered variable within ω_{QRS} to render sweeping tractable. A search space for the Saltelli forward optimization of ω_{QRS} was defined by prescribing physiologically-constrained

Table 4

Fascicular definition used for sampling initiation within $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ based on experimental knowledge of the HPS Durrer et al. (1970); Atkinson et al. (2011); Massing and James (1976). For each fascicular site, the location of root point $\mathbf{b} \in D_{\text{UTC}}$, radius in the apico-basal-circumferential plane $\delta_{\varphi z}$, transmural extent δ_{ρ} and activation time t_a are prescribed.

	\mathbf{b}						
	z_0	ρ_0	φ_0	ν_0	$\delta_{\varphi z,0}$	$\delta_{\rho,0}$	$t_{a,0}$
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{sf}}$	0.5 ± 0.25	0.0	0.0 ± 1.0	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{pf}}$	0.5 ± 0.25	0.0	-1.0 ± 1.0	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{af}}$	0.8 ± 0.25	0.0	2.6 ± 1.0	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}$	0.6 ± 0.25	1.0	1.0 ± 1.0	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}$	0.4 ± 0.25	≤ 0.25	0.1 ± 1.0	+1	0.05	0.05	≤ 25

corridors around a baseline HPS $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ configured to match the Durrer et al. (1970) activation pattern.

The baseline HPS within $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ was configured using the fixed number of $N = 5$ fascicles, three in the LV – anterior, septal, and posterior – defined by $\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{sf}}$, $\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{pf}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{lv},\text{af}}$, and two in the RV – septum and free wall corresponding lateral anchoring site of the moderator band – defined by $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}$, respectively Durrer et al. (1970); Massing and James (1976); Ten Tusscher and Panfilov (2008). All sites were assumed to have an approximate thicknesses of 5 percent of the ventricular wall ($\delta_{\rho} \approx 0.05$) relating to a layer of ≈ 25 cells assuming a cell diameter of $\approx 20\mu\text{m}$ Opie (2004); Massing and James (1976). Additionally, fascicular sites were constrained to small-disks $\delta_{\varphi z} = 0.05$. Then, fascicular root points \mathbf{b} were bounded by $z_0 \pm 0.25$ and $\varphi_0 \pm 1.0$ from the baseline fascicle configuration in agreement with general fascicular regions within the literature Massing and James (1976); Durrer et al. (1970) and other modeling studies Cranford et al. (2018); Sahli Costabal et al. (2016); Ten Tusscher and Panfilov (2008). Due to the thinness of the RV wall and its interaction with the precordial leads, the timing, sizing, and transmural extent of the $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}$ site was additionally varied such that $\rho_0 \leq 0.25$. To control the initiation of propagation in the ventricular myocardium, activation timings were prescribed to all fascicles. By default, all LV sites and the $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}$ were activated simultaneously at $t = 0\text{ms}$. Only the $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}$ was fired later with a slight delay $t_{\text{rv},\text{mod}} \leq 25.0$ Durrer et al. (1970). The parameter feature $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ could then be expressed by:

$$\omega_{\text{QRS}} = (z_{\text{lv},\text{sf}}, z_{\text{lv},\text{pf}}, z_{\text{lv},\text{af}}, z_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}, z_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}, \varphi_{\text{lv},\text{sf}}, \varphi_{\text{lv},\text{pf}}, \varphi_{\text{lv},\text{af}}, \varphi_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}, \varphi_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}, \rho_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}, t_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}). \quad (16)$$

A summary of the HPS parameters within $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ and their bounds are summarized in Table 4.

Subsequently, keeping the L_2 optimal activation parameter sub-vector $\omega_{\text{QRS},\text{opt}}$ constant, key parameters governing repolarization and its signature in the T-wave according to Eqs. (2)-(3) were sampled in feature sub-vector ω_{T} to obtain $\omega_{\text{T},\text{opt}}$. The sub-vector ω_{T} can be expressed as follows:

$$\omega_{\text{T}} = (\text{APD}_{\min}, \text{APD}_{\max}, z_d, \rho_d, \varphi_d, \nu_d). \quad (17)$$

A bounded corridor for ω_{T} was selected where APD_{\min} and APD_{\max} were allowed to vary between the extreme values of 150 and 400 ms estimated from the 12 lead ECG for S_1 . Namely, the approximate intervals between the end of QRS and the onset of the T-wave and the onset of QRS and the end of the T-wave, respectively, within the 12 lead ECG for S_1 . Accordingly, simulations were defined within the time range of $0 \leq t < 450\text{ms}$ corresponding to the respective end of the T-wave. The weights for blending the repolarization gradients were chosen to result in earlier repolarization within epicardium, apex, posterior-side, and right ventricle Opthof et al. (2016, 2017); Keller et al. (2012). The minimal and maximal

Fig. 3. Two-step approach for optimizing parameters within ω_{opt} using parameter subvectors ω_{QRS} , ω_T , and ω_0 .

Table 5

Physiologically-constrained bounds for repolarization parameters within ω_T . APD_{min} and APD_{max} are given in ms.

	APD_{min}	APD_{max}	z_d	ρ_d	φ_d	ν_d
min	150	250	0	-1	0	-1
max	250	400	1	0	1	0

sampling bounds used for ω_T are summarized in Table 5. Values were not initialized around a default repolarization template.

A schematic of the two-step optimization scheme can be seen in Fig. 3. In total, ω_{QRS} and ω_T comprised 12 and 6 parameters, respectively. All other parameters also influencing the activation or repolarization phase defined within ω_0 were taken as constant as detailed in Section 2.5.4 and (15). Assuming 1000 samples per parameter within the Saltelli sampling schematic defined by 500(k + 2) Saltelli (2002), where k denotes the number of parameters, a total of 7000 and 4000 simulations were conducted for the sweeps pertaining to the fitting of the QRS complex and T-wave. All simulated ECGs were low-pass filtered at 60Hz and scaled according to the single aligned heartbeat in $\mathbf{y}_m(t)$ for subject S_1 . Goodness of fit for each sample was ranked according to the loss $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}_m, \mathbf{y}_s(\omega_{QRS,i}))$ defined as the L_2 norm formulated in (14).

2.6. Assessing the approximation errors of the RELF ECG model

Approximation errors of the RELF ECG model due to simplifying assumptions and coarser spatial resolution affecting the source representation were assessed. A reference gold-standard R-D bidomain simulation using TNNP was first computed on the 250 μ m resolution for S_1 over a duration of $T_s = 450ms$ to cover one entire ventricular repolarization cycle using the parameter vector ω_{opt} found during subsequent parameterization as detailed in Section 2.5.5, but modified by Table 7. The combined effect of using an Eikonal-determined activation sequence and lead-field projection upon source distribution and ECG morphology was then investigated by executing the exact same simulation setup used for generating the reference with the RELF⁺ model. Morphological differences stemming from the use of the simplified ionic model were

Table 6

Parameters relating to the HPS subscribed within the parameter vector ω_{val} used to perform model assessment.

	b						
	z_{val}	ρ_{val}	ϕ_{val}	ν_{val}	$\delta_{\phi z, val}$	$\delta_{\rho, val}$	$t_{a, val}$
$\mathbf{x}_{iv, sf}$	0.7	0.0	0.0	-1	0.25	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{iv, pf}$	0.5	0.0	-0.4	-1	0.25	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{iv, af}$	0.75	0.0	0.8	-1	0.4	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{rv, sf}$	0.8	0.95	0.0	-1	0.4	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{rv, mod}$	0.5	0.5	0.0	+1	0.4	0.1	12

Table 7

Settings for repolarization and tuned conductivity settings for the R-D model using a physiological TNNP model.

Feature	Parameter	Value	Unit
Conductivities	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, il}$	0.14	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, el}$	0.05	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, in}$	0.02	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, en}$	0.03	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, it}$	0.02	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{myo, et}$	0.03	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, il}$	1.84	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, el}$	0.65	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, in}$	0.17	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, en}$	0.22	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, it}$	0.17	S/m
	$\mathcal{G}_{se, et}$	0.22	S/m
	Repolarization	APD_{min}	300
APD_{max}		300	ms
\mathbf{q}_w		0	-

explored by generating a corresponding RELF⁺ simulation with the tuned model as defined in Table 2. Resolution-dependencies were then investigated by conducting a RELF⁺ simulation with a model of subject S_1 at decreasing mesh resolutions of 1000 μ m, 500 μ m and 250 μ m. As RELF⁺ is computationally significantly more expensive, RELF⁻ was finally compared to RELF⁺ on the 1000 μ m for S_1 using the tuned model to quantify the impact of neglecting diffusion upon the T-wave.

The setup for assessing the accuracy of the RELF model used a preliminary alternative parameter vector ω_{val} that included con-

Table 8

Approximate timings for all 12 models for the entire anatomical workflow and construction of the reference frame \mathcal{X} in seconds run on 16 cores for a target model resolution of $1000\mu\text{m}$, $500\mu\text{m}$ and $250\mu\text{m}$. All timings are reported following an initial segmentation time of approximately 4h.

	Resolution		
	250m	500m	1000m
Meshing	6703	1226	765 ± 118
Extraction of Ω_{biv} , Ω_{iv} , and Ω_{rv}	1012	121	38 ± 6
Generation of surfaces for BCs	1439	169	33 ± 5
BN solutions	4329	483	69 ± 11
UVC generation	213	22	3 ± 1
UTC generation	8632	1165	423 ± 59
Inclusion of SE Layer	669	58	8 ± 1
Myocardial Fiber Generation	1489	67	9 ± 1
ECG Localization	44	7	3

stant model parameters as specified by ω_0 , but with a modified HPS as defined by Table 6. Namely, all sites were prescribed a radial dimension of either 0.25 or 0.40 ($\delta_{\text{paz}} \in \{0.25, 0.4\}$) in accordance with LV bundle branch distances as reported in [Massing and James \(1976\)](#). LV sites were confined to the endocardium ($\rho = 0$) while both $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, sf}}$ and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, mod}}$ sites were presumed to reside subendocardially. More specifically, the $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, sf}}$ site almost reached the RV septal endocardium ($\rho = 0.95$) and $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, mod}}$ was rooted in the middle of the RV wall ($\rho = 0.5$). Due to the thinness of the RV wall, a transmural extent of $\delta_{\rho} \approx 0.1$ was also prescribed to $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, mod}}$. The $\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv, mod}}$ was initiated at $t = 12\text{ms}$ with all other sites activating simultaneously at $t = 0\text{ms}$. In contrast to the default value of 2.0ms^{-1} as specified by [Durrer et al. \(1970\)](#), a value of 2.5ms^{-1} within the fast-conducting SE layer according to [Kassebaum and Van Dyke \(1966\)](#) was prescribed for $c_{\text{se, v}}$.

As the MS model could not be tuned for R-D models to achieve high velocities of 2.5ms^{-1} as specified within the initialized parameter vector ω_{val} (Table 1), the computationally more expensive TNNP was used [Ten Tusscher and Panfilov \(2006\)](#). Conductivities were tuned for an average spatial resolution of $250\mu\text{m}$ to the CVs and anisotropy ratios as specified in Table 1 to give resultant values as defined in Table 7. An artificial increase in sodium conductance ($G_{\text{Na}} = 250\mu\text{ A / cm}^2$) within TNNP was required. As a direct mapping between parameters within the TNNP model and APD does not exist, a single action potential profile was generated for the entirety of the ventricular domain Ω_{biv} by setting $\text{APD}_{\text{min}} = \text{APD}_{\text{max}} = 300$ and $\mathbf{q}_w = \mathbf{0}$. Thus, for the sake of relative comparisons between model variants effects of repolarization heterogeneities upon the T-wave were ignored. The MS model settings were tuned to ensure close comparability with the action potential profile resulting from the TNNP model as defined within Table 2.

3. Results

3.1. Workflow performance

Detailed timings for each processing stage required for anatomical twinning and the establishment of a reference frame for all 12 models are given in Table 8. Time spent on segmentation and registration amounted to approximately 4h when performed by an operator familiar with cardiac anatomy. Afterwards, mesh generation was executed automatically to achieve an average resolution of $1206.52\mu\text{m}$ within Ω_{tor} and $998.49\mu\text{m}$ within Ω_{biv} suitable for solving of the forward R-E model. Using the label fields \mathcal{I} defined on the mesh as input, automatic construction of the reference frame required approximately 742s for the $1000\mu\text{m}$ model.

Simulation timings required for functional twinning for subject S_1 are given in Table 9. Lead field computation for the model re-

Table 9

Approximate timings for subject S_1 for simulation using RELF workflow in seconds run on 16 cores for a target model resolution of $1000\mu\text{m}$, $250\mu\text{m}$ and $500\mu\text{m}$.

	Resolution		
	250 μm	500 μm	1000 μm
Lead Field Computation	6569	550	168
Setup	1084	66	16
RELF ⁻ Solver Time	560	54	8
Total	8216	671	192

quired a one-time computational cost of approximately 167seconds for the $1000\mu\text{m}$ model. Given no subsequent change in parameters that may trigger lead field computation, the execution of the forward RELF⁻ model to simulate 450ms activity and the corresponding ECGs from a given parameter vector ω required only 24s on a desktop computer with 16 cores including setup. The actual solver time of the RELF⁻ amounted to 8s. Timings are reported for average resolutions of $250\mu\text{m}$ and $500\mu\text{m}$ when targeting higher spatial resolutions compatible with higher resolution R-D models for S_1 .

3.2. Fidelity evaluation of the fast-forward ECG model

The computational fidelity of the fast forward ECG model using RELF⁻ was evaluated by comparing the computed source distributions and the associated clinical 12 lead ECGs to those computed by a gold standard R-D bidomain model. Four potential sources of errors were considered that stem from inherent assumptions made by using a R-E monodomain source model without diffusion solved at a coarse grid of $1000\mu\text{m}$ combined with the lead field method to recover electrograms at the ECG lead locations.

First, the activation sequence in the R-E model is determined by an Eikonal solution. Thus, any effects of downstream loading due to the presence of a bath, boundary effects due to the sealed intracellular space or curvature upon wave front shape and velocity are neglected. Fig. 4C reveals that these effects marginally alter the distribution of sources in the heart. Rather, computed extracellular potentials ϕ_e at the body surface with the RELF⁺ model were virtually identical during depolarization. Minor differences were witnessed during repolarization when diffusion is neglected in the RELF⁻ model (see Fig. 4E).

Secondly, gains in speed of the fast forward ECG model result from the ability to simulate action potential propagation on coarser meshes without spatial resolution artifacts of R-D models [Niederer et al. \(2011b\)](#). As shown in Fig. 4A, the representation of cardiac sources with the RELF⁻ model on a coarser grid using resolutions of $500\mu\text{m}$ and $1000\mu\text{m}$ did not entail any significant deviations from the high resolution source model computed at a resolution of $250\mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 4C).

Finally, although the RELF⁺ model required an approximate run time of 213s, when comparing RELF⁺ and RELF⁻ model only very minor differences in the T-wave were observed. Neglecting diffusion in the computationally much more efficient RELF⁻ model is therefore an admissible choice.

Our analysis demonstrates that generated ECGs are indiscernible from the gold standard bidomain ECG, only marginal deviations were witnessed (Fig. 4C) which are deemed negligible as these were well below the limits of overall observational and residual uncertainties of ECG measurements. Thus, the fast forward RELF⁻ model produces bidomain equivalent ECG with close to real time performance ($\approx 8\text{s}$) using a desktop computer which is a fraction of the compute costs of a bidomain ECG ($\approx 1010\text{s}$) using high-performance computing (High-performance Computing (HPC)) with 576 compute cores.

Fig. 4. Evaluation of fast forward RELF⁻ model against a gold standard R-D bidomain model. (A) Comparison of extracellular potential distribution ϕ_e at the time instant 35ms corresponding to peak R in lead I. All RELF potentials for rendering were recovered using pseudo-bidomain. (B) Comparison of action potentials between the TNNP (black) and MS (red) ionic models. (C) ECGs obtained with R-D bidomain with TNNP (blue), RELF⁺ with TNNP (red), and RELF⁺ using MS (purple) computed on the high resolution mesh $\delta x = 250\mu\text{m}$. (D) ECGs obtained with RELF⁺ with MS solved at mesh resolutions of $\delta x = 1000\mu\text{m}$ (orange), $\delta x = 500\mu\text{m}$ (cyan), and $\delta x = 250\mu\text{m}$ (purple). (E) ECGs obtained with RELF⁺ (orange) and RELF⁻ (green) using MS. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 10

Optimal parameters relating to the HPS within the parameter sub-vector $\omega_{\text{QRS,opt}}$ found within the sampled parameter search space.

b							
	z_{opt}	ρ_{opt}	ϕ_{opt}	v_{opt}	$\delta_{\varphi z,\text{opt}}$	$\delta_{\rho,\text{opt}}$	$t_{a,\text{opt}}$
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{iv},\text{sf}}$	0.61	0.0	0.73	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{iv},\text{pf}}$	0.47	0.0	-1.36	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{iv},\text{af}}$	0.82	0.0	1.94	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{sf}}$	0.73	1.0	-0.04	-1	0.05	0.05	0
$\mathbf{x}_{\text{rv},\text{mod}}$	0.63	0.11	0.21	+1	0.05	0.05	15.3

Table 11

Optimal repolarization parameter sub-vector $\omega_{\text{T,opt}}$ found within the sampled parameter search space. APD_{min} and APD_{max} in ms.

	APD_{min}	APD_{max}	z_d	ρ_d	φ_d	v_d
	167.00	305.28	0.96	-0.11	-0.01	-0.01

3.3. Parameter estimation

The ability of representing all space-varying parameter fields as a function of \mathcal{X} and of computing accurate ECGs sufficiently fast renders automated sweeping of the parameter space feasible. This ability is demonstrated using a forward optimization with Saltelli sampling to identify parameter sub-vectors ω_{QRS} and ω_{T} governing morphology of QRS complex and T-wave for subject S_1 . The optimal parameter sub-vector ω_{QRS} producing the smallest L_2 loss $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}_m, \mathbf{y}_s(\omega_{\text{T},i}))$ is given in Table 10 and the subsequent optimal ω_{T} is reported in Table 11.

The achieved goodness of fit for the combined optimal QRS complex and T-wave attained from $\omega_{\text{QRS,opt}}$ and $\omega_{\text{T,opt}}$ in comparison to both the clinically-measured ECG and the initialized sub-vectors $\omega_{\text{QRS},0}$ and $\omega_{\text{T},0}$ is illustrated in Fig. 5C. Resultant activation and repolarization maps are shown in Fig. 5A and Fig. 5B, respectively.

4. Discussion

This study reports on the development of a novel and highly automated workflow that addresses both the *anatomical* and *functional* twinning stages of creating a high-fidelity CDT. As a demonstration of feasibility, anatomical twinning was first performed on a cohort of 12 subjects. The ventricular EP was then replicated in terms of the clinical 12-lead ECG to demonstrate functional twinning for a single healthy subject.

To generate anatomical CDTs, automated four-chamber multi-label segmentation was carried out, followed by manual inspection, correction and registration with the torso segmentation. While multi-label segmentation remained the only processing stage in our workflow that could not be fully automated, requiring some manual corrections, the overall processing time for building a single anatomical CDT remained within a clinically viable time frame of < 4 hours.

At the core of our ECG-based functional twinning workflow are three key advancements crucial for the future clinical integration of CDTs limiting previous studies. First, the introduction of a reference frame \mathcal{X} within the anatomical model allows the manipulation of all parameters within our parameter vector $\omega(\mathcal{X})$ to enable unattended sweeps of the full parameter space, including important space-dependent parameters relating to the HPS, conduction and repolarization properties. Secondly, the comprehensive parameter vector used in the forward ECG model is rich and flexible enough such that the most relevant factors governing ventricular activation and repolarization can be taken into account. This facilitates, in principle, the replication the broader variability of ECG

morphologies in the wider population. Thirdly, the RELF forward ECG model is computationally efficient, allowing the computation of ECGs at gold standard biophysical fidelity with close to real-time performance.

4.1. Related work

Parameter inference is the most challenging task of generating a CDT. Fast models of ventricular EP are of critical importance that allow balancing of biophysical fidelity, parameter identifiability and computational cost. Previously used forward ECG models offered either biophysical fidelity Potse (2018) or computational efficiency Zettinig et al. (2014), but not both at the same time. Though classic R-D bidomain models serve as a ground truth reference for simulating ECG Potse et al. (2014), R-D models used in previous studies using either a full bidomain model Cardone-Noott et al. (2016) or monodomain source model combined with a lead field approach Potse (2018) required hundreds of compute cores on HPC facilities with execution times at the order of hours rendering them clinically impractical. Lightweight and fast ECG models have thus been proposed within basic research to overcome limitations due to the significant computational costs inherent to R-D models that have been predominantly used in recent clinical modeling studies Prakosa et al. (2018); Arevalo et al. (2016); Cartoski et al. (2019). However, these models have been thus far limited in terms of their ability to accurately replicate physiologically comprehensive ECGs due to either limitations inherent to the model formulation or the lack of a sufficiently biophysically-detailed parameter vector that is easily steerable by optimization.

For example, a novel efficient forward EP model based on a Lattice-Boltzmann method to represent cardiac sources and the boundary element method (Boundary Element Method (BEM)) to forward transfer cardiac sources to the potentials at the body surface has been reported by Zettinig et al. (2014). The reported performance facilitates computations at the order of seconds, comparable to the RELF model used in our study, enabling fine-grained exploration of the model parameter space. 19 models of dilated cardiomyopathy patients were thus built and sampled to provide enough data for building a regression model to facilitate the fast parameterization of diffusivity of LV and RV subendocardial layers, used as a surrogate for the HPS, from two extracted scalar features – the duration of the QRS complex, QRS_d , and the angle of the electrical axis based on leads I and II, α .

However, the ability of their model to replicate measured clinical ECGs was limited. First, as the fascicular system in the LV was considered fixed, the model inherently assumes that no variability in fascicular topology among humans exists since neither anatomy nor the makeup of the HPS were represented. However, the large number of differing topologies found in the HPS Demoulin and Kulbertus (1972); Ono et al. (2009) suggest that location, topology of the terminal HPS anchoring in the ventricular subendocardium, penetration depth, transmural extent, antero-grade and retrograde activation delays across Purkinje-ventricular junctions Boyle et al. (2010) are likely to be variable among humans. Otherwise, the variability in morphology could all be explained by purely anatomical factors. Additionally, the metrics utilized within the study are not sufficiently specific. A vast number of markedly different configurations can lead to the same axis angle α , and although a close match between velocity and QRS_d can be achieved due to a direct relationship, the velocity adjustments needed are highly non-unique. A thorough quantitative comparison between computed and measured wave forms was not performed, only a qualitative visual comparison for the limb leads was shown (see Fig. 17 in Zettinig et al. (2014)) that shows a promising match in the parameter used for fitting, but also striking

Fig. 5. HPS including fascicular locations, activation map and repolarization map for the baseline parameter vectors $\omega_{QRS,0}$ and $\omega_{T,0}$ (A), as well as for the optimal parameter sub-vectors $\omega_{QRS,opt}$ and $\omega_{T,opt}$ (B) are shown. The resultant optimized ECGs obtained with the baseline parameter vector $\omega_{QRS,opt}$ without T-wave parameterization (C) and the combined optimal parameter vector ω_{opt} (D) is shown in comparison to the measured reference ECG. Within C and D, black coloration corresponds to the reference subject ECG, blue corresponds to the ECG attained with $\omega_{QRS,opt}$, and red corresponds to the complete optimized ECG using ω_{opt} . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

ing discrepancies in morphological features in most ECG leads. A comparison with the more sensitive precordial leads was also not shown.

Inverse modeling studies have also been used to gain insight into the spatio-temporal distribution of electrical sources at the surface or throughout the volume of the heart from electrical measurements attained at the surface of the heart or the body surface [Cluitmans et al. \(2018\)](#); [Relan et al. \(2011\)](#); [Dhamala et al. \(2020\)](#) and are thus highly useful for CDTs. For instance, inverse models have been introduced to aid in the interpretation of clinical observations such as the identification of the location of a focal trigger [Sapp et al. \(2020\)](#). In general, however, they cannot be used to make prognosis predictions

of interventions such as pacing therapies [Strocchi et al. \(2020\)](#); [Swenson et al. \(2020\)](#) as the models fail to describe the underlying mechanisms behind ventricular EP and focus only on the sources. For instance, the forward ECG model used within the software ECG-Sim [van Oosterom and Oostendorp \(2004\)](#) is based on an enhanced double layer source model that performs ECG prediction in real-time but cannot compute the ventricular activation sequence. Rather, activation times are prescribed over a closed ventricular surface comprising epicardium, left and right ventricular endocardium as well as the basal junction between ventricles and atria that had to be reconstructed first by solving an inverse problem. As such, the utility of the model is limited with regard to generating personalized EP CDTs.

4.2. Biophysical fidelity of the fast forward ECG model

The key advantage of the RELF model is its ability to reconcile the competing demands between speed and fidelity. The RELF model computes ECGs on a desktop computer within seconds, comparable to Zettinig et al. (2014) at comparable degree of fidelity as a gold standard bidomain model solved in simulations on supercomputers using hundreds of compute cores lasting on the order of hours Potse et al. (2006); Cardone-Noott et al. (2016). The computational gains of the RELF model are achieved by making simplifying assumptions which may, to some extent, impact ECG fidelity. However, our analyses demonstrate that losses in accuracy are negligible, when put in perspective with the overall observational and residual uncertainties of ECG registration.

4.2.1. Loading effects

Artifacts in lower resolution R-D models with regard to CVs and wave front shape are inevitable Niederer et al. (2011b); Clayton et al. (2011), but can be avoided using a R-E model Neic et al. (2017). However, loading effects that modulate CV, anisotropy and wave front shapes alter extracellular potential field dictating the ECG. As propagation in the R-E model is driven by an Eikonal solution these effects are not taken into account. These primarily include i) bath loading mediated by the feedback of the extracellular potential field on wave front propagation. The higher conductivity of the bath relative to the interstitial space induces a drag effect that accelerates wave front speed within an electrotonic distance to the tissue-bath interface. Wave front shape is thus altered, leading to a V-shaped wave front profile that affects the extracellular potential field along the tissue-bath interface Henriquez et al. (1996); Bishop and Plank (2011b); Bishop et al. (2011); Bernus and Vigmond (2015); ii) locally altered potential fields in the electrotonic vicinity of a stimulus site or a Purkinje-ventricular junction where wave front propagation is initiated Spach and Dolber (1986); iii) wave front acceleration toward tissue boundaries or at sites of wave front collision, where no downstream capacitance must be discharged due to the sealed intracellular space Spach and Dolber (1986); iv) wave front curvature reducing or accelerating CV for convex or concave wave front shapes Cabo et al. (1994), respectively, due to an altered source-sink ratio; v) electrotonic loading during repolarization acting to smooth out intrinsic repolarization gradients. At early repolarization sites repolarization is slowed down by electrotonic current flow from later repolarizing sites and, vice versa, repolarization is hastened at later repolarizing sites.

These loading effects combined had only a minor subtle impact on activation and the QRS complex, but mostly limited to the leads V1 and V2 that are closest to the cardiac sources (see Fig. 4). Effects on repolarization were even smaller. Heterogeneity in repolarization was taken into account based on a map APD(\mathbf{x}), as given by Eq. (3), which led to a smooth variation in APD throughout the ventricles. In contrast to previous studies where APD was set based on labeled regions Bishop et al. (2011) stark intrinsic differences in APD across region boundaries were avoided which diminished the role of diffusion during repolarization. This is confirmed by Fig. 4E. The T-wave produced by the fast RELF⁻ model that fully ignored diffusion is virtually indiscernible from the T-wave produced by the computationally more RELF⁺ model that resolves diffusion.

4.2.2. Coarsened spatial resolution

Using a coarse spatial resolution of $\approx 1000\mu\text{m}$ may affect the fidelity of the source representation. The spatial extent of the depolarization wave front is $< 1000\mu\text{m}$ for propagation along the fibers, and may be $\ll 1000\mu\text{m}$ in other directions. Particularly along a sheet normal direction the spatial extent of the wave front is at a cellular size scale. As such, source distribution and local

extracellular dipole may not be properly represented on a coarser mesh due to spatial under sampling. However, at a $1000\mu\text{m}$ resolution only very minor scaling effects were witnessed, leading to an attenuation in ECG signal magnitude, but – as the ECG is recorded in the far-field further away from the cardiac sources – with limited impact on its morphology. For modeling intracardiac electrograms recorded in the immediate vicinity to the sources such as device electrodes that are placed directly at a ventricular surface or are screwed into the myocardial wall, a more pronounced spatial resolution effects are anticipated. More pronounced effects may also appear for slower CVs as they occur for higher anisotropies and increased wave front curvatures or under pathologies leading to slow decremental conduction, with wave front speeds $\ll 0.2\text{ms}^{-1}$. However, a detailed investigation of resolution effects during slow conduction was beyond the scope of this study.

ECG signal attenuation is anticipated from inspecting the right hand side of Eq. (12) that acts as source term setting up the extracellular potential field. The numerical approximation of the second derivative of $V_m(\mathbf{x})$ with respect to space degrades with reducing resolution. However, minor deviations in ECG magnitude are of limited diagnostic relevance.

4.2.3. Computation of ECGs using lead field

Another factor potentially limiting the fidelity of ECGs is the use of a lead field approach Geselowitz (1989); Potse (2018) instead of a bidomain model to recover extracellular potentials. On theoretical grounds Geselowitz (1989) it is expected that the lead field approach yields the exact same extracellular electrograms as a full bidomain model. This has been shown in previous numerical studies Potse (2018) and is in line with our observations here, suggesting correctness of our implementation.

For obtaining high fidelity ECGs efficiently the lead field approach has proven beneficial. The computational costs of the lead field evaluation of Eq. (11) are virtually negligible, amounting only to a fraction of the costs of solving the elliptic portion of the bidomain equation in Eq. (12). Lead field based computation of one time step of a single ECG lead involves one matrix-vector multiplication of a stiffness matrix with the point-wise vector product between Z and V_m .

The cost of computing the lead field Z is non-negligible – at the order of seconds – and equivalent to the cost of solving Eq. (12). However, Z is computed only once during initialization. The right hand side of the lead field equation given in Eq. (11) is constant, comprising only two unitary Dirac current sources. The left hand side is constant as well, only changes in conductivity tensors, either by altering eigenvalues or fiber and sheet axes, would trigger a re-computation of Z . Thus, pre-computed lead fields Z could be stored on disk and read in when needed.

Our lead field implementation differs from previous reports where a non-conformal heart-torso model was used Potse (2018). Using a R-D monodomain source model enforced a high spatial resolution of $200\mu\text{m}$ for the heart. Using a conformal mesh of the same discretization for the torso led to prohibitively expensive simulations. Thus, lower spatial resolution hanging background meshes were used for computing Z in the torso, with additional costs incurring from down sampling and projecting V_m onto the coarser torso. In our FEM simulation a conformal mesh was used, where the torso mesh was adaptively coarsened with distance to the cardiac surfaces Prassl et al. (2009). This kept the overall degrees of freedom within tractable bounds.

Other previous ECG modeling studies relied on a BEM formulation Zettinig et al. (2014). In comparison our FEM-based lead field approach offers a number of advantages. The inclusion spatial variation in anisotropic tissue conductivities within the torso is readily achieved Keller et al. (2010). Further, the lead field ECG

can be computed robustly, at any desirable resolution using standard finite-element routines. This is not necessarily the case with the BEM. The BEM features high pass properties which may produce noisy torso potential distributions, typically requiring down sampling and smoothing of the source distribution over all cardiac surfaces [Stenroos \(2009\)](#); [Fischer et al. \(1998\)](#).

A potential disadvantage of the FEM-based lead field approach is the need for a discrete representation of the torso volume. This is not the case with a BEM model where only a closed cardiac surface and the torso surface are needed. Thus, the BEM lends itself more readily to applications where location and orientation of the heart is varied within the torso, or when shape models are used to perturb the cardiac anatomy to study the influence of anatomical factors upon the ECG. In practice, this inconvenience can be mitigated by automating the torso volume mesh generation. In our implementation this is readily achieved with *mesh-tool* [Neic et al. \(2020\)](#). While meshing the entire combined heart-torso mesh at a resolution of $1000\mu\text{m}$ lasted $\approx 733\text{s}$, re-meshing the torso volume alone was much faster, lasting ≈ 1 minute.

4.2.4. Computational efficiency

The RELF model yields computational speedups of orders of magnitude, facilitating the computation of gold standard ECGs with close to real-time performance. In our prototype implementation the simulation of a 450ms ECG required an $\approx 8\text{s}$ solution time using the RELF⁻ model, corresponding to a real-time lag factor of ≈ 16 . Using the RELF⁺ model entailed a significant increase in run time, deteriorating the real-time lag factor to ≈ 213 . With the RELF⁺ model [Eq. \(6\)](#) was solved semi-implicitly, necessitating the solution of a linear system. An explicit solution may be feasible, but constraints apply on the choice of time step Δt that are dictated by the CFL condition of the smallest elements in the unstructured mesh. As shown previously [Niederer et al. \(2011a\)](#), this problem can be mitigated by breaking up the parabolic time step to maintain stability, but this has not been investigated.

The computational efficiency achieved suffices, in principle, for many applications, but further speedups may be necessary depending on the desired level of fidelity, the available time frame and the used parameter identification approach. In this study a stochastic Saltelli sampling approach was employed on reduced feature vectors ω_{QRS} and ω_{T} to reduced dimensionality, with additional physiological box constraints to limit search space. The parameter vector producing the ECG for S_1 shown in [Fig. 5](#) was selected out of 16k samples as it produced the smallest L_2 loss. When performed on a desktop computer the total execution time would amount to ≈ 15 hours. As the sampling constitutes an embarrassingly parallel computing problem the parameter search could be scaled down using HPC clusters. Nonetheless, a fine-grained brute force sweep over the entire physiologically conceivable parameter space may require further increases in computational efficiency or the use of simpler surrogate models.

ECG models of comparable efficiency have been used previously [Zettinig et al. \(2014\)](#); [van Oosterom and Oostendorp \(2004\)](#), but these are not able to replicate the underlying EP problem at the same level of fidelity. The efficiency of the Lattice-Boltzmann based model due to [Zettinig et al. \(2014\)](#) is comparable to the RELF model. The study reported 2.8s and 21.7s for a forward EP run on an isotropic grid of 1.5mm and 0.7mm resolution. A closely related approach has been reported in [Pezzuto et al. \(2017\)](#) There, a fixed action potential shape was used and shifted as a function of eikonal-based activation times to represent cardiac sources on a regular finite difference grid of 1mm resolution. Using a GPU implementation ECGs on a patient-derived heart-torso model could be computed even faster than with our model, with a real-time lag of ≈ 2 .

The performance reported in ECG modeling studies relying on R-D models appears insufficient for the purpose of creating high fidelity CDTs. The study by [Potse \(2018\)](#) used a R-D monodomain source model in combination with the lead-field approach to simulate ECGs in a human heart-torso model. The use of a finite difference method on a regular grid combined with the high resolution of $200\mu\text{m}$ led to a punitively vast computational load, with a heart-torso mesh comprising up to 3.3 billion nodes. Despite the fast execution times of $\approx 180\text{s}$ achieved with 896 HPC CPU cores, corresponding to a real-time lag factor of 360, the computational resources are prohibitive for performing a parameter search and post-processing of the vast amounts of data generated by a single run raises tractability issues. Similarly, the study by [Cardonne-Noot](#) used a R-D bidomain formulation [Cardone-Noot et al. \(2016\)](#). A bi-ventricular model discretized at $400\mu\text{m}$ was embedded in a torso model in an anatomically plausible orientation. The combined heart-torso model comprised 3.25 million nodes. Using 240 CPU cores for simulating a QRS complex of 150milli second lasted 30 minutes, resulting in a real-time lag factor of $\approx 12e3$. Thus, this model is less efficient than the RELF by three orders of magnitude, without offering any advantages in terms of biophysical fidelity under sinus conditions. However, it must be noted that this model allows re-entrant activation, not currently possible with the RELF model, and thus could be advantageous in this regard.

4.3. Functional twinning

Functional twinning procedures were fully automated and did not require any operator intervention. All parameters ω relating to ventricular EP during healthy sinus rhythm in our forward ECG model were abstractly expressed within the reference frame \mathcal{X} as functions of space, allowing their unattended manipulation and, thus, the automation of functional twinning. These included all complex space-dependent entities such as the fascicular structure of the HPS, as well as heterogeneities in CV and repolarization properties.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first forward ECG model incorporating an entirely abstract functional description of the HPS, ventricular conduction and repolarization. Previous studies assumed a fixed set of fascicular locations [Zettinig et al. \(2014\)](#), prescribed activation over the entire endocardium [Cardone-Noot et al. \(2016\)](#) or varied activation sites manually [Potse et al. \(2014\)](#). Automated functional twinning under the likely assumption that the HPS is variable among humans can therefore not be achieved with these approaches. Also topologically realistic models of the HPS appear less suitable for building CDTs without additional parameters for steering the spatial distribution of the Purkinje-ventricular junction [Zimmerman et al. \(2009\)](#); [Sahli Costabal et al. \(2016\)](#). The direct use of topological realistic HPS models also does not necessarily yield physiologically meaningful ECGs, suggesting that the activation sequences they produce are not representative of healthy ventricles. Thus, ECG modeling studies using an explicit representation of the HPS require additional network topology optimization procedures to adjust the endocardial stimulation profile [Kahlmann et al. \(2017\)](#).

The achieved match in QRS morphology in all limb leads for the single subject during sinus rhythm ([Fig. 5](#)) resulting from $\omega_{\text{QRS,opt}}$ is indicative of the validity of the underlying model assumptions made on the HPS. Only morphological discrepancies were witnessed in the R-progression and amplitudes in the precordial leads, namely V1 and V2. Discrepancies can be contributed to the generation of strong cardiac sources in the RV free wall being in close proximity to the precordial electrodes on the torso surface. As indicated by the morphology attained in the precordial leads during comparison in [Fig. 4](#), which exhibit dampened V1 and V2 amplitudes and better R-progression, different parameters for ω may

mitigate this discrepancy and can be accounted for by including more variable model parameters and widening the search corridors in the Saltelli sweep for ω_{QRS} .

The optimal simulated T-wave morphology as obtained by $\omega_{T,opt}$ deviated less markedly from the measured ECG (Fig. 5). Deviations may be attributed to the definition of parameters controlling repolarization that rely exclusively on a combination of linear gradients and do not take into account repolarization heterogeneity due to coupling of the HPS with the myocardium Walton et al. (2014). Furthermore, given the usage of the binary sign function σ in anterior-posterior gradient, a non-smooth transition in repolarization gradients along this direction may generate unphysiological morphology in the T-wave. A better match may also be attainable given an improved match in the QRS complex due to the dependency of repolarization on activation.

4.3.1. Metrics for measuring similarity between ECG signals

Automation of functional twinning depends on robust loss metrics for evaluating the goodness of fit. Similarity between measured and simulated ECG was quantified using an L_2 loss which was used then for ranking instantiations of the feature vector where the parameter vector producing the smallest loss was considered the best approximation of a measured ECG. Visual inspections of the ranked ECGs suggest that ranking based on L_2 loss is meaningful. That is, parameter vectors producing a smaller loss appeared morphologically more similar than those producing a higher loss. However, as the utilized L_2 loss is not robust with respect to temporal shift and signal magnitudes, simulated ECGs were aligned first in time and scaled in a pre-processing step. This is based on the rationale that all relevant information is encoded in the wave form, and not in the signal magnitude. Scaling was applied collectively, applying the same time shift and magnitude scaling to all 12 ECG traces to preserve all relations between the leads.

In view of using gradient-based optimization methods instead of global sampling robust loss metrics that lead to a smooth loss landscapes are needed. However, investigating the properties of the L_2 landscape or using of other loss metrics was beyond the scope of our study. Other candidate metrics comprise correlation coefficients, dynamic time warping Sakoe and Chiba (1978) or Wasserstein distances Villani (2008). Also, the use of lower dimensional targets such as the vectorcardiogram Gemmell et al. (2020) could be advantageous. Similarity could also be measured by comparing features extracted from the ECG, such as QRS duration or electrical axis angle Zettinig et al. (2014). Feature-based loss reduces the dimensionality of the problem, but discards important information that may help to reveal details of the ventricular EP and also requires robust ECG analysis software. Using QRS duration and electrical axis angle only as done in Zettinig et al. (2014) does not appear to offer sufficiently discriminatory power, classifying ECGs of vastly different morphology as similar.

4.3.2. Parameter identification strategies

Functional twinning was only performed for the single subject as a demonstration of feasibility and not the entire cohort due to the high computational cost of Saltelli sampling. More efficient strategies are thus needed to find an optimal parameter vector that produces the best representation of an observed ECG for additional models in the cohort. A simple but potentially inefficient approach is a global optimization strategy based on sampling. However, despite the efficiency of the forward ECG model, a fine-grained sweep of the high dimensional parameter space is not feasible as this would necessitate on the order of millions of simulation runs. To reduce the computational costs, we applied a forward optimization approach in the form of Saltelli sampling to demonstrate feasibility. While this approach offers advantages over other global sam-

pling methods, the incurring compute costs are still non-negligible as the parameter vector ω is still high-dimensional. To render the Saltelli sampling tractable, only a subset of the parameter vector ω was considered variable, with other important parameters kept constant. In addition, extensive *a priori* knowledge was used to define sufficiently narrow physiological search corridors for both activation and repolarization heterogeneity in the human ventricles as detailed more thoroughly in Section 2.5.5. A thorough global sensitivity analysis of parameters in our parameter vector could have helped to better understand the relative influence of individual components of ω on simulation outcomes, but this has not yet been performed.

Combining better physiological priors, suitable optimization techniques and learning algorithms show promise to achieve faster parameterization of CDTs for various clinical applications Dhamala et al. (2020). Since all space-dependent entities of ω can be altered on the fly within an optimization loop our model is, in principle, compatible with gradient-based optimization strategies. For example, derivative-free optimization or iterative gradient-based optimization methods that compute loss with respect to the parameters are likely to perform better Grandits et al. (2020), but also rely on a robust loss metric and a reasonably smooth and convex loss landscape that allows to derive search directions.

Machine learning and statistical methods for building regression models that approximate the inverse function of the ECG model could also provide an efficient means of finding an initial parameterization, as shown in Zettinig et al. (2014); Dhamala et al. (2020). Such models however build on the assumption that the ECG morphology is mostly defined by the EP characteristics governing activation and repolarization, and to a lesser extent by the anatomy of heart and torso. Otherwise, regression models have to be trained again from scratch for each new anatomy, rendering such approaches less attractive. However, generative models Dhamala et al. (2020) have recently been formulated that are not only robust against anatomical variation, but also can be used to reduce the high-dimensionality of encoding ventricular EP.

4.4. Limitations

The automation of our anatomical twinning workflow depends on sufficiently-accurate multi-label segmentations which constituted the largest computational time sink in the entire workflow of approximately 4 hours as stated in Section 3.1. While large investments have already been made toward the development and training of neural networks for automated clinical cardiac segmentation Murphy et al. (2011); Khened et al. (2019); Payer et al. (2017), such methods are tailored to a specific imaging modality and often require manual correction. However, a fully automated multi-label segmentation of all four cardiac chambers might be achieved in the future Chen et al. (2020). Similarly, an approach for automated, user-independent segmentation of the torso must also be considered. Depending on the imaging modality, fully-automatic threshold-based segmentation may be possible for the torso and lungs given high contrast with other tissues. While atlas-based torso models have been successfully used in previous studies Zettinig et al. (2014), such models neglect patient-specific anatomy and typically do not account for all thoracic tissues.

In contrast to previous related studies Zettinig et al. (2014) that quantified goodness of fit for a number of cases, functional twinning in this proof-of-concept study was limited to a single subject. Zettinig et al. reported good correlation in terms of surrogate metrics such as the angle of the electrical axis in the frontal plane computed from leads I and II, but visual inspection of the shown limb leads were suggestive of notable differences in activation and repolarization patterns between model and patient (in

Zettinig et al. (2014), see leads II, III and aVF in Fig. 17, the more sensitive precordial leads are not shown).

In our study we focused on identifying a parameter vector that yielded an ECG of compelling morphological similarity for one subject. The described strategy would also work for other subjects in the cohort which were, by chance, electrically similar. For instance, according to the Cabrera system all subjects featured a normal axis. However, the ECG morphology is surprisingly sensitive to subtle changes in model parameters. For instance, transmural extent and location of the moderator band fascicle had a significant impact on the QRS in leads V1-V3. As such, departing from the same initial five fascicular setup a significantly more expansive parameter search may be required to obtain ECGs that are of comparable fidelity as suggested in Keller et al. (2009); Cranford et al. (2018), particularly for subjects that are not close to the Durrer observations. Despite the efficiency of the RELF model, the cost of sampling would add up, particularly for cases not sufficiently close to the five fascicular setup based on the observations of Durrer Durrer et al. (1970).

To further advance the method and fully automate the procedure a brute force attack based on stochastic sampling may be inefficient. To ascertain that the measured ECG falls within the envelope of the simulated ECGs would require the inclusion of parameters such as the activation timings of LV fascicles, which would further increase the dimensionality of the problem. Further research is required to better understand the relative contributions of all factors involved as performed in Cranford et al. (2018), to use smarter sampling methods that factor in sensitivities to individual factors or the use of combined global-local optimization methods that allow a more directed search. Such strategies also depend on robust similarity measures which also require further research. Ranking according to the L_2 norm as used in here correlated well with visual inspection though, that is, a lower norm was indicative of a closer morphological similarity.

Spatial descriptions of the entities relating to the HPS were kept simple and relied on the prescription of earliest activation sites. Fascicles were modeled as cylindrical disks and the effect of the fast spread of depolarization mediated by the complex topology of the HPS was approximated by a faster conducting SE layer of a given transmural and apico-basal extent Hyde et al. (2015). Considering that fundamental aspects of the ventricular activation by the HPS remain poorly understood, it seems likely that our representation of the HPS is too simplistic. It must also be noted that a fascicular-based approach for defining activation profiles is suitable only for modeling sinus activation. In other scenarios where the retrograde activation of the HPS plays a role, such as the modeling of bundle branch block or pacing Boyle et al. (2010), the use of fascicle-based activation profiles is inadequate from a mechanistic point of view. However, once an appropriate activation profile has been identified the abstract representations of fascicles and SE layer can be replaced with a topological representation of the HPS. An automated workflow for this task can be readily implemented using our reference frame and HPS generation algorithms Palamara et al. (2014); Sahli Costabal et al. (2016); Strocchi et al. (2020).

Further investigation is also needed to better understand the impact of using the MS ionic model to describe cellular dynamics on resultant ECG morphology. The MS ionic model is highly simplified and as such is not able to represent the full complexity of heterogeneity in AP morphologies. However, more recent ionic models such as the Bueno-Orovio model Bueno-Orovio et al. (2008), are able to provide physiologically more accurate representations at comparable computational costs.

No consideration was currently made for ventricular EP disorders that would be a necessary extension for clinical applications. However, many electrical pathologies can be modeled with

minimal effort through the prescription or extension of ω while other disorders pose a greater effort. Substrate-based diseases, such as myocardial infarction, require defining additional heterogeneous regions with altered conductive properties leading to additional mesh manipulation and ionic model tuning. Diseases of the conduction system, namely bundle branch blocks or ectopic beats generating premature ventricular contractions, could be generated through the addition, subtraction, or alteration of stimulus sites as defined by \mathbf{x}_s . Pacing protocols are similarly implemented Relan et al. (2011). However, ECG simulations under rhythm disorders of reentrant phenotype are not feasible with the current RELF model as the underlying Eikonal model driving activation does not support reentrant patterns. Further advanced alterations to both activation and repolarization profiles might be needed as well as the incorporation of atrial-ventricular conduction to replicate ECGs produced by various rhythm disturbances. However, by design, our reference frame lends itself naturally to the definition of arbitrarily complex parameter variations within an anatomically meaningful system.

Finally, the solution of the inverse problem of ventricular EP is non-unique. As such, we cannot conclude with certainty that the activation and repolarization sequence of the forward model replicates the subject's EP, even if the simulated and observed ECG during sinus rhythm were in perfect agreement. However, based on the experiences gathered in this study, the ECG is highly sensitive to model parameters. As such, the odds of computing the same ECG with markedly different activation and repolarization sequences are extremely unlikely.

Settling this open question prompts for further model validation using data that contains both information about the cardiac ventricular sources and ECGs attained from the torso surface. These should be recorded under a broader range of conditions that yield different activation and repolarization patterns, to be able to split data for training and testing as seen in Giffard-Roisin et al. (2016); Dhamala et al. (2020). Such data sets were not available for the healthy volunteers in this proof-of-concept study, but are routinely acquired in the clinic during invasive mapping studies or device implant. However, such clinical data are of limited spatial resolution, mapping locations are afflicted with uncertainties and information on ventricular sources in the depth of the 3D myocardium is not available. Invasive experimental studies within animal models that are able to provide activation and repolarization mapping data at high spatial resolutions in 3D throughout the myocardial wall Zenger et al. (2020) could alternatively be used. However, it is known that there are differences in ventricular EP between humans and various animal models.

5. Conclusion

This proof-of-concept study reports on the development of a novel workflow for the highly automated generation of high-fidelity CDTs replicating ventricular EP. Non-invasive 12-lead clinical standard ECGs providing a global but sensitive view on overall ventricular EP are used as a metric driving model parameterization and assessment of similarity between model and data. The workflow addresses both the *anatomical* and *functional* components of creating a CDT. At the core of our ECG-based functional twinning workflow are three key advancements crucial for generating *virtual cohorts* of CDTs at scale limiting previous studies.

First, usage of the novel RELF model increased computational efficiency to clinically-feasible time scales ($\ll 1$ day) with minimal impact on resulting ECG fidelity as confirmed through assessment against the gold standard bidomain model. Second, introduction of a reference frame \mathcal{X} within the anatomical model allows unattended manipulation of all parameters within our parameter vector ω to enable sweeps of the full parameter space including

important space-dependent parameters relating to the HPS, conduction, and repolarization properties. Lastly, the parameter vector used in the forward ECG model is rich and flexible enough such that the most relevant factors governing ventricular activation and repolarization can be taken into account to replicate, in principle, the broader variability of ECG morphologies in the wider population.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary material

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References

- Arevalo, H.J., Vadakkumpadan, F., Guallar, E., Jebb, A., Malamas, P., Wu, K.C., Trayanova, N.A., 2016. Arrhythmia risk stratification of patients after myocardial infarction using personalized heart models. *Nat. Commun.* 7.
- Atkinson, A., Inada, S., Li, J., Tellez, J.O., Yanni, J., Sleiman, R., Allah, E.A., Anderson, R.H., Zhang, H., Boyett, M.R., Dobrzynski, H., 2011. Anatomical and molecular mapping of the left and right ventricular his-Purkinje conduction networks. *J. Mol. Cell. Cardiol.* 51 (5), 689–701. doi:10.1016/j.yjmcc.2011.05.020.
- Augustin, C.M., Neic, A., Liebmann, M., Prassl, A.J., Niederer, S.A., Haase, G., Plank, G., 2016. Anatomically accurate high resolution modeling of human whole heart electromechanics: a strongly scalable algebraic multigrid solver method for nonlinear deformation. *J. Comput. Phys.* 305, 622–646.
- Bayer, J., Blake, R., Plank, G., Trayanova, N., 2012. A novel rule-based algorithm for assigning myocardial fiber orientation to computational heart models. *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 40 (10), 2243–2254.
- Bayer, J., Prassl, A.J., Pashaei, A., Gomez, J.F., Frontera, A., Neic, A., Plank, G., Vigmond, E.J., 2018. Universal ventricular coordinates: a generic framework for describing position within the heart and transferring data. *Med. Image Anal.* 45, 83–93.
- Bernus, O., Vigmond, E., 2015. Asymptotic wave propagation in excitable media. *Phys. Rev. E* 92 (1), 010901. doi:10.1103/PhysRevE.92.010901.
- Besl, P.J., McKay, N.D., 1992. Method for registration of 3-d shapes. In: *Sensor fusion IV: control paradigms and data structures*, 1611. International Society for Optics and Photonics, pp. 586–606.
- Bishop, M.J., Plank, G., 2011. Bidomain ecg simulations using an augmented monodomain model for the cardiac source. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 58 (8), 2297–2307.
- Bishop, M.J., Plank, G., 2011. Representing cardiac bidomain bath-loading effects by an augmented monodomain approach: application to complex ventricular models. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 58, 1066–1075. doi:10.1109/TBME.2010.2096425.
- Bishop, M.J., Vigmond, E., Plank, G., 2011. Cardiac bidomain bath-loading effects during arrhythmias: interaction with anatomical heterogeneity. *Biophys. J.* 101, 2871–2881. doi:10.1016/j.bpj.2011.10.052.
- Boyle, P.M., Deo, M., Plank, G., Vigmond, E.J., 2010. Purkinje-mediated effects in the response of quiescent ventricles to defibrillation shocks. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 38 (2), 456–468.
- Bueno-Orovio, A., Cherry, E.M., Fenton, F.H., 2008. Minimal model for human ventricular action potentials in tissue. *J. Theor. Biol.* 253 (3), 544–560. doi:10.1016/j.jtbi.2008.03.029.
- Burgess, M.J., Harumi, K., Abildskov, J., 1966. Application of a theoretic t-wave model to experimentally induced t-wave abnormalities. *Circulation* 34 (4), 669–678.
- Cabo, C., Pertsov, A.M., Baxter, W.T., Davidenko, J.M., Gray, R.A., Jalife, J., 1994. Wave-front curvature as a cause of slow conduction and block in isolated cardiac muscle. *Circ. Res.* 75 (6), 1014–1028.
- Cardone-Noott, L., Bueno-Orovio, A., Mincholé, A., Zemzemi, N., Rodriguez, B., 2016. Human ventricular activation sequence and the simulation of the electrocardiographic qrs complex and its variability in healthy and intraventricular block conditions. *EP Europace* 18 (suppl_4), iv4–iv15.
- Cartoski, M.J., Nikolov, P.P., Prakosa, A., Boyle, P.M., Spevak, P.J., Trayanova, N.A., 2019. Computational identification of ventricular arrhythmia risk in pediatric myocarditis. *Pediatr. Cardiol.* 40 (4), 857–864.
- Chen, C., Qin, C., Qiu, H., Tarroni, G., Duan, J., Bai, W., Rueckert, D., 2020. Deep learning for cardiac image segmentation: a review. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* 7, 25.
- CIBC, 2016. Seg3D: Volumetric Image Segmentation and Visualization. Scientific Computing and Imaging <http://www.seg3d.org>.
- Clayton, R.H., Bernus, O., Cherry, E.M., Dierckx, H., Fenton, F.H., Mirabella, L., Panfilov, A.V., Sachse, F.B., Seemann, G., Zhang, H., 2011. Models of cardiac tissue electrophysiology: progress, challenges and open questions. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* 104 (1–3), 22–48. doi:10.1016/j.pbiomolbio.2010.05.008.
- Clerc, L., 1976. Directional differences of impulse spread in trabecular muscle from mammalian heart. *J. Physiol. (Lond.)* 255 (2), 335–346.
- Cluitmans, M., Brooks, D.H., MacLeod, R., Dössel, O., Guillem, M.S., van Dam, P.M., Svehlikova, J., He, B., Sapp, J., Wang, L., Bear, L., 2018. Validation and opportunities of electrocardiographic imaging: from technical achievements to clinical applications. *Front. Physiol.* 9, 1305. doi:10.3389/fphys.2018.01305.
- Corral-Acero, J., Margara, F., Marciniak, M., Rodero, C., Loncaric, F., Feng, Y., Gilbert, A., Fernandes, J.F., Bukhari, H.A., Vajdan, A., Martinez, M.V., Santos, M.S., Shamohammadi, M., Luo, H., Westphal, P., Leeson, P., DiAchille, P., Gurev, V., Mayr, M., Geris, L., Pathmanathan, P., Morrison, T., Cornelussen, R., Prinzen, F., Delhaas, T., Doltra, A., Sitges, M., Vigmond, E.J., Zacur, E., Grau, V., Rodriguez, B., Remme, E.W., Niederer, S., Mortier, P., McLeod, K., Potse, M., Pueyo, E., Bueno-Orovio, A., Lamata, P., 2020. The 'digital Twin' to enable the vision of precision cardiology. *Eur. Heart J.* 1–11. doi:10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa159.
- Costa, C.M., Hoetzl, E., Rocha, B.M., Prassl, A.J., Plank, G., 2013. Automatic parameterization strategy for cardiac electrophysiology simulations. In: *Computing in Cardiology Conference (CinC)*, 2013. IEEE, pp. 373–376.
- Cranford, J.P., OHara, T.J., Villongco, C.T., Hafez, O.M., Blake, R.C., Loscalzo, J., Fattebert, J.-L., Richards, D.F., Zhang, X., Glosli, J.N., et al., 2018. Efficient computational modeling of human ventricular activation and its electrocardiographic representation: a sensitivity study. *Cardiovasc. Eng. Technol.* 9 (3), 447–467.
- Crozier, A., Augustin, C., Neic, A., Prassl, A., Holler, M., Fastl, T., Hennemuth, A., Bredies, K., Kuehne, T., Bishop, M., et al., 2016. Image-based personalization of cardiac anatomy for coupled electromechanical modeling. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 44 (1), 58–70.
- Demoulin, J.C., Kulbertus, H.E., 1972. Histopathological examination of concept of left hemiblock. *Br. Heart J.* 34 (8), 807–814.
- Dhamala, J., Bajracharya, P., Arevalo, H.J., Sapp, J.L., Horáček, B.M., Wu, K.C., Trayanova, N.A., Wang, L., 2020. Embedding high-dimensional bayesian optimization via generative modeling: parameter personalization of cardiac electrophysiological models. *Med. Image Anal.* 62, 101670.
- Draper, M.H., Weidmann, S., 1951. Cardiac resting and action potentials recorded with an intracellular electrode. *J. Physiol. (Lond.)* 115, 74–94.
- Durrer, D., Van Dam, R.T., Freud, G., Janse, M., Meijler, F., Arzbaecher, R., 1970. Total excitation of the isolated human heart. *Circulation* 41 (6), 899–912.
- Fernandez-Teran, M., Hurler, J., 1982. Myocardial fiber architecture of the human heart ventricles. *Anat. Rec.* 204 (2), 137–147.
- Fischer, G., Tilg, B., Wach, P., Lafer, G., Rucker, W., 1998. Analytical validation of the beam application of the beam to the electrocardiographic forward and inverse problem. *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 55 (2), 99–106.
- Gemmell, P., Gillette, K., Balaban, G., Rajani, R., Vigmond, E., Plank, G., Bishop, M., 2020. A computational investigation into rate-dependant vectorcardiogram changes due to specific fibrosis patterns in non-ischemic dilated cardiomyopathy. *Comput. Biol. Med.*
- Geselowitz, D.B., 1989. On the theory of the electrocardiogram. *Proc. IEEE* 77 (6), 857–876.
- Giffard-Roisin, S., Jackson, T., Fovargue, L., Lee, J., Delingette, H., Razavi, R., Ayache, N., Sermesant, M., 2016. Noninvasive personalization of a cardiac electrophysiology model from body surface potential mapping. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 64 (9), 2206–2218.
- Glukhov, A.V., Fedorov, V.V., Lou, Q., Ravikumar, V.K., Kalish, P.W., Schuessler, R.B., Moazami, N., Efimov, I.R., 2010. Transmural dispersion of repolarization in failing and non failing human ventricle. *Circ. Res.* 106 (5), 981.
- Grandits, T., Gillette, K., Neic, A., Bayer, J., Vigmond, E., Pock, T., Plank, G., 2020. An inverse eikonal method for identifying ventricular activation sequences from epicardial activation maps. *J. Comput. Phys.* 419, 109700. doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2020.109700.
- Gulrajani, R.M., Roberge, F.A., Savard, P., 1989. *Comprehensive Electrocardiology*. Pergamon Press, New York, pp. 237–288.
- Halhuber, M.J., Günther, R., Ciresa, M., 2012. *ECG: An introductory course a practical introduction to clinical electrocardiography*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Helm, P., Beg, M.F., Miller, M.I., Winslow, R.L., 2005. Measuring and mapping cardiac fiber and laminar architecture using diffusion tensor mr imaging. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1047 (1), 296–307.
- Henriquez, C.S., Muzikant, a.L., Smoak, C.K., 1996. Anisotropy, fiber curvature, and bath loading effects on activation in thin and thick cardiac tissue preparations: simulations in a three-dimensional bidomain model. *J. Cardiovasc. Electrophysiol.* 7 (5), 424–444.
- Hyde, E.R., Behar, J.M., Claridge, S., Jackson, T., Lee, A.W.C., Remme, E.W., Sohal, M., Plank, G., Razavi, R., Rinaldi, C.A., Niederer, S.A., 2015. Beneficial effect on cardiac resynchronization from left ventricular endocardial pacing is mediated by early access to high conduction velocity tissue: electrophysiological simulation study. *Circ. Arrhythmia Electrophysiol.* 8 (5), 1164–1172. doi:10.1161/CIRCEP.115.002677.

- Kahlmann, W., Poremba, E., Potyagaylo, D., Dössel, O., Loewe, A., 2017. Modelling of patient-specific purkinje activation based on measured ECGs. *Curr. Dir. Biomed. Eng.* 3 (2), 171–174. doi:10.1515/cdbme-2017-0177.
- Kassebaum, D.G., Van Dyke, A.R., 1966. Electrophysiological effects of isoproterenol on purkinje fibers of the heart. *Circ. Res.* 19 (5), 940–946.
- Keith, A., Flack, M.W., 2004. The auriculo-ventricular bundle of the human heart. *Annals of noninvasive electrocardiology: the official journal of the International Society for Holter and Noninvasive Electrocardiology, Inc* 9 (4), 400.
- Keller, D., Kalayciyan, R., Dössel, O., Seemann, G., 2009. Fast creation of endocardial stimulation profiles for the realistic simulation of body surface eegs. In: *World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering*, September 7–12, 2009, Munich, Germany. Springer, pp. 145–148.
- Keller, D.U., Weber, F.M., Seemann, G., Dössel, O., 2010. Ranking the influence of tissue conductivities on forward-calculated eegs. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 57 (7), 1568–1576.
- Keller, D.U., Weiss, D.L., Dössel, O., Seemann, G., 2012. Influence of heterogeneities on the genesis of the t-wave: a computational evaluation. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 59 (2), 311–322.
- Khened, M., Kollerathu, V.A., Krishnamurthi, G., 2019. Fully convolutional multi-scale residual densenets for cardiac segmentation and automated cardiac diagnosis using ensemble of classifiers. *Med. Image Anal.* 51, 21–45.
- Kucherenko, S., Albrecht, D., Saltelli, A., 2015. Exploring multi-dimensional spaces: a Comparison of Latin Hypercube and Quasi Monte Carlo Sampling Techniques(May). 1505.02350.
- Le Guyader, P., Trelles, F., Savard, P., 2001. Extracellular measurement of anisotropic bidomain myocardial conductivities. i. theoretical analysis. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* 29 (10), 862–877.
- Li, G.-R., Feng, J., Yue, L., Carrier, M., 1998. Transmural heterogeneity of action potentials and i_{to1} in myocytes isolated from the human right ventricle. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 275 (2), H369–H377.
- Luo, S., Johnston, P., 2010. A review of electrocardiogram filtering. *J. Electrocardiol.* 43 (6), 486–496.
- Massing, G.K., James, T.N., 1976. Anatomical configuration of the his bundle and bundle branches in the human heart.. *Circulation* 53 (4), 609–621.
- Mitchell, C.C., Schaeffer, D.G., 2003. A two-current model for the dynamics of cardiac membrane. *Bull. Math. Biol.* 65 (5), 767–793.
- Murphy, K., Van Ginneken, B., Reinhardt, J.M., Kabus, S., Ding, K., Deng, X., Cao, K., Du, K., Christensen, G.E., Garcia, V., et al., 2011. Evaluation of registration methods on thoracic ct: the empire10 challenge. *IEEE Trans. Med. Imaging* 30 (11), 1901–1920.
- Neic, A., Meshtool. <https://bitbucket.org/aneic/meshtool/src/master/>.
- Neic, A., Campos, F.O., Prassl, A.J., Niederer, S.A., Bishop, M.J., Vigmond, E.J., Plank, G., 2017. Efficient computation of electrograms and eegs in human whole heart simulations using a reaction-eikonal model.. *J. Comput. Phys.* 346, 191–211. doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2017.06.020.
- Neic, A., Gsell, M.A., Karabelas, E., Prassl, A.J., Plank, G., 2020. Automating image-based mesh generation and manipulation tasks in cardiac modeling workflows using meshtool. *SoftwareX* 11, 100454.
- Niederer, S., Mitchell, L., Smith, N., Plank, G., 2011. Simulating human cardiac electrophysiology on clinical time-scales.. *Front. Physiol.* 2, 14. doi:10.3389/fphys.2011.00014.
- Niederer, S.A., Aboelkassem, Y., Cantwell, C.D., Corrado, C., Coveney, S., Cherry, E.M., Delhaas, T., Fenton, F.H., Panfilov, A.V., Pathmanathan, P., Plank, G., Riabiz, M., Roney, C.H., Dos Santos, R.W., Wang, L., 2020. Creation and application of virtual patient cohorts of heart models.. *Philos. Trans. A. Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 378 (2173), 20190558. doi:10.1098/rsta.2019.0558.
- Niederer, S.A., Kerfoot, E., Benson, A.P., Bernabeu, M.O., Bernus, O., Bradley, C., Cherry, E.M., Clayton, R., Fenton, F.H., Garny, A., Heidenreich, E., Land, S., Maleckar, M., Pathmanathan, P., Plank, G., Rodriguez, J.F., Roy, I., Sachse, F.B., Seemann, G., Skavhaug, O., Smith, N.P., 2011. Verification of cardiac tissue electrophysiology simulators using an n-version benchmark. *Philos. Trans. A. Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 369, 4331–4351. doi:10.1098/rsta.2011.0139.
- Ono, N., Yamaguchi, T., Ishikawa, H., Arakawa, M., Takahashi, N., Saikawa, T., Shimada, T., 2009. Morphological varieties of the purkinje fiber network in mammalian hearts, as revealed by light and electron microscopy.. *Arch. Histol. Cytol.* 72 (3), 139–149.
- van Oosterom, a., Oostendorp, T.F., 2004. ECGSIM: An interactive tool for studying the genesis of QRST waveforms.. *Heart* 90 (2), 165–168.
- Opie, L.H., 2004. *Heart physiology: From cell to circulation*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Ophof, T., Janse, M.J., Meijborg, V.M., Cinca, J., Rosen, M.R., Coronel, R., 2016. Dispersion in ventricular repolarization in the human, canine and porcine heart. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* 120 (1–3), 222–235.
- Ophof, T., Remme, C.A., Jorge, E., Noriega, F., Wiegerinck, R.F., Tasiyam, A., Beekman, L., Alvarez-Garcia, J., Munoz-Guijosa, C., Coronel, R., et al., 2017. Cardiac activation–repolarization patterns and ion channel expression mapping in intact isolated normal human hearts. *Heart Rhythm* 14 (2), 265–272.
- Palamara, S., Vergara, C., Catanzariti, D., Faggiano, E., Pangrazzi, C., Centonze, M., Nobile, F., Maines, M., Quarzeroni, A., 2014. Computational generation of the purkinje network driven by clinical measurements: the case of pathological propagations.. *Int. j. numer. method. biomed. eng.* 30 (12), 1558–1577. doi:10.1002/cnm.2689.
- Payer, C., Štern, D., Bischof, H., Urschler, M., 2017. Multi-label whole heart segmentation using cnns and anatomical label configurations. In: *International Workshop on Statistical Atlases and Computational Models of the Heart*. Springer, pp. 190–198.
- Pezzuto, S., Kal'avský, P., Potse, M., Prinzen, F.W., Auricchio, A., Krause, R., 2017. Evaluation of a rapid anisotropic model for ECG simulation. *Front. Physiol.* 8 (MAY). doi:10.3389/fphys.2017.00265.
- Potse, M., 2018. Scalable and accurate eeg simulation for reaction-diffusion models of the human heart. *Front. Physiol.* 9, 370.
- Potse, M., Dubé, B., Richer, J., Vinet, A., Gulrajani, R.M., 2006. A comparison of monodomain and bidomain reaction-diffusion models for action potential propagation in the human heart. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 53 (12), 2425–2435.
- Potse, M., Krause, D., Kroon, W., Murzilli, R., Muzzarelli, S., Regoli, F., Caiani, E., Prinzen, F.W., Krause, R., Auricchio, A., 2014. Patient-specific modelling of cardiac electrophysiology in heart-failure patients. *Europace* 16 (suppl_4), iv56–iv61.
- Potse, M., Vinet, A., Ophof, T., Coronel, R., 2009. Validation of a simple model for the morphology of the t wave in unipolar electrograms. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 297 (2), H792–H801.
- Prakosa, A., Arevalo, H.J., Deng, D., Boyle, P.M., Nikolov, P.P., Ashikaga, H., Blauer, J.J., Ghafoori, E., Park, C.J., Blake, R.C., et al., 2018. Personalized virtual-heart technology for guiding the ablation of infarct-related ventricular tachycardia. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* 1.
- Prassl, A.J., Kicking, F., Ahammer, H., Grau, V., Schneider, J.E., Hofer, E., Vigmond, E.J., Trayanova, N.A., Plank, G., 2009. Automatically generated, anatomically accurate meshes for cardiac electrophysiology problems.. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 56, 1318–1330. doi:10.1109/TBME.2009.2014243.
- Relan, J., Pop, M., Delingette, H., Wright, G.A., Ayache, N., Serresant, M., 2011. Personalization of a cardiac electrophysiology model using optical mapping and mri for prediction of changes with pacing. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* 58 (12), 3339–3349.
- Remme, C.A., Verkerk, A.O., Hoogaars, W.M.H., Aanhaanen, W.T.J., Scicluna, B.P., Annink, C., van den Hoff, M.J.B., Wilde, A.A.M., van Veen, T.A.B., Veldkamp, M.W., de Bakker, J.M.T., Christoffels, V.M., Bezzina, C.R., 2009. The cardiac sodium channel displays differential distribution in the conduction system and transmural heterogeneity in the murine ventricular myocardium.. *Basic Res. Cardiol.* 104, 511–522. doi:10.1007/s00395-009-0012-8.
- Roberts, D.E., Hersh, L.T., Scher, A.M., 1979. Influence of cardiac fiber orientation on wavefront voltage, conduction velocity, and tissue resistivity in the dog.. *Circ. Res.* 44 (5), 701–712.
- Roberts, D.E., Scher, A.M., 1982. Effect of tissue anisotropy on extracellular potential fields in canine myocardium in situ. *Circ. Res.* 50 (3), 342–351.
- Roney, C.H., Pashaei, A., Meo, M., Dubois, R., Boyle, P.M., Trayanova, N.A., Cochet, H., Niederer, S.A., Vigmond, E.J., 2019. Universal atrial coordinates applied to visualization, registration and construction of patient specific meshes. *Med. Image Anal.* 55, 65–75. doi:10.1016/j.media.2019.04.004.
- Sahli Costabal, F., Hurtado, D.E., Kuhl, E., 2016. Generating purkinje networks in the human heart.. *J. Biomech.* 49 (12), 2455–2465. doi:10.1016/j.jbiomech.2015.12.025.
- Sakoe, H., Chiba, S., 1978. Dynamic programming algorithm optimization for spoken word recognition. *IEEE Trans Acoust 26* (1), 43–49.
- Saltelli, A., 2002. Making best use of model evaluations to compute sensitivity indices. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 145 (2), 280–297.
- Saltelli, A., Annoni, P., Azzini, I., Campolongo, F., Ratto, M., Tarantola, S., 2010. Variance based sensitivity analysis of model output. design and estimator for the total sensitivity index. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 181 (2), 259–270.
- Sapp, J.L., Zhou, S., Wang, L., 2020. Mapping ventricular tachycardia with electrocardiographic imaging.
- Sebastian, R., Ordas, S., Plank, G., Rodriguez, B., Vigmond, E.J., Frangi, A.F., 2008. Assessing influence of conductivity in heart modelling with the aim of studying cardiovascular diseases. In: *Medical imaging 2008: physiology, function, and structure from medical images*, 6916. International Society for Optics and Photonics, p. 691627.
- Sermesant, M., Moireau, P., Camara, O., Sainte-Marie, J., Andriantsimivavona, R., Cirmman, R., Hill, D.L., Chapelle, D., Razavi, R., 2006. Cardiac function estimation from mri using a heart model and data assimilation: advances and difficulties. *Med. Image Anal.* 10 (4), 642–656.
- Spach, M.S., Dolber, P.C., 1986. Relating extracellular potentials and their derivatives to anisotropic propagation at a microscopic level in human cardiac muscle. evidence for electrical uncoupling of side-to-side fiber connections with increasing age.. *Circ. Res.* 58 (3), 356–371.
- Spach, M.S., Huang, S.-n., Armstrong, S.I., Canett JR, R.V., 1963. Demonstration of peripheral conduction system in human hearts. *Circulation* 28 (3), 333–338.
- Stenroos, M., 2009. The transfer matrix for epicardial potential in a piece-wise homogeneous thorax model: the boundary element formulation. *Physics in Medicine & Biology* 54 (18), 5443.
- Stephenson, R.S., Atkinson, A., Kottas, P., Perde, F., Jafarzadeh, F., Bateman, M., Iaizzo, P.A., Zhao, J., Zhang, H., Anderson, R.H., et al., 2017. High resolution 3-dimensional imaging of the human cardiac conduction system from microanatomy to mathematical modeling. *Sci. Rep.* 7 (1), 1–13.
- Streeter, D.D., Spotnitz, H.M., Patel, D.P., Ross, J., Sonnenblick, E.H., 1969. Fiber orientation in the canine left ventricle during diastole and systole. *Circ. Res.* 24 (3), 339–347.
- Strocchi, M., Lee, A.W.C., Neic, A., Bouyssier, J., Gillette, K., Plank, G., Elliott, M.K., Gould, J., Behar, J.M., Sidhu, B., Mehta, V., Bishop, M.J., Vigmond, E.J., Rinaldi, C.A., Niederer, S.A., 2020. His bundle and left bundle pacing with optimised atrio-ventricular delay achieve superior electrical synchrony over endocardial and epicardial pacing in left bundle branch block patients.. *Heart Rhythm* doi:10.1016/j.hrthm.2020.06.028.

- Swenson, D.J., Taepke, R.T., Blauer, J.J.E., Kwan, E., Ghafoori, E., Plank, G., Vigmond, E., MacLeod, R.S., DeGroot, P., Ranjan, R., 2020. Direct comparison of a novel antitachycardia pacing algorithm against present methods using virtual patient modeling.. *Hear. Rhythm* doi:10.1016/j.hrthm.2020.05.009.
- Ten Tusscher, K., Panfilov, A.V., 2008. Modelling of the ventricular conduction system. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* 96 (1–3), 152–170.
- Ten Tusscher, K.H., Panfilov, A.V., 2006. Cell model for efficient simulation of wave propagation in human ventricular tissue under normal and pathological conditions. *Physics in Medicine & Biology* 51 (23), 6141.
- Vigmond, E., Dos Santos, R.W., Prassl, A., Deo, M., Plank, G., 2008. Solvers for the cardiac bidomain equations. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* 96 (1), 3–18.
- Villani, C., 2008. *Optimal transport: Old and new*. Springer Science & Business Media. Google-Books-ID: hV8o5R7_5tkC.
- Walton, R.D., Martinez, M.E., Bishop, M.J., Hocini, M., Haïssaguerre, M., Plank, G., Bernus, O., Vigmond, E.J., 2014. Influence of the purkinje-muscle junction on transmural repolarization heterogeneity.. *Cardiovasc. Res.* 103 (4), 629–640. doi:10.1093/cvr/cvu165.
- Zenger, B., Good, W.W., Bergquist, J.A., Burton, B.M., Tate, J.D., Berkenbile, L., Sharma, V., MacLeod, R.S., 2020. Novel experimental model for studying the spatiotemporal electrical signature of acute myocardial ischemia: atranslational platform. *Physiol. Meas.* 41 (1), ab64b9. doi:10.1088/1361-6579/ab64b9.
- Zettinig, O., Mansi, T., Neumann, D., Georgescu, B., Rapaka, S., Seegerer, P., Kayvanpour, E., Sedaghat-Hamedani, F., Amr, A., Haas, J., et al., 2014. Data-driven estimation of cardiac electrical diffusivity from 12-lead ecg signals. *Med. Image Anal.* 18 (8), 1361–1376.
- Zhuang, X., Li, L., Payer, C., Štern, D., Urschler, M., Heinrich, M.P., Oster, J., Wang, C., Smedby, Ö., Bian, C., et al., 2019. Evaluation of algorithms for multi-modality whole heart segmentation: an open-access grand challenge. *Med. Image Anal.* 58, 101537.
- Zimmerman, V., Sebastian, R., Bijnens, B., Frangi, A., 2009. Modeling the purkinje conduction system with a non deterministic rule based iterative method. In: 2009 36th Annual Computers in Cardiology Conference (CinC). IEEE, pp. 461–464.